

Mistra C2B2
Co-Creating
Better Blue

D4.1 PROTOTYPE LIVINGLABS METHODOLOGY & INITIAL GUIDANCE WITH GENERIC CASE COMPENDIUM

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D4.1 PROTOTYPE LIVINGLABS METHODOLOGY & INITIAL GUIDANCE WITH GENERIC CASE COMPENDIUM

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Abstract of deliverable	This report sets out the context, rationale and conceptual grounding for the initial C2B2 methodology for establishing and running LivingLabs in the three case studies of the Mistra C2B2 programme. It describes the implementation of the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology and presents the initial version of the generic compendium for the early stages of the methodology.

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Executive Summary

The overarching aim of the Mistra-C2B2 project *Co-creating a better blue* (hereafter, the C2B2 programme, or C2B2) is to foster participatory and adaptive ocean governance and management in Sweden, by triggering transformative change towards a more sustainable blue economy and a more inclusive, science-based and cross-sectoral approach to marine resources.

A key objective of the C2B2 programme is to demonstrate in practice in Living Labs how transformative change towards participatory and science-based ecosystem governance of a sustainable blue economy can be achieved.

The work in WP4 *Co-creation of participatory ocean governance in LivingLabs* primarily serves to achieve this objective by establishing and running LivingLabs (LL) in three case study areas in Sweden: in the Gulf of Bothnia (i.e. LivingLab North); in the Baltic Sea (i.e. LivingLab Est) and in the Kattegat-Skagerrak region (i.e. LivingLab West).

This report (D4.1) is the first WP4 Deliverable and it provides the C2B2 project partners and C2B2 LLs leads with an overview of the prototype LivingLabs methodology to be applied to the C2B2 context. It also provides the C2B2 LLs leads with initial guidance – in the form of a generic case compendium – on how to set up, launch and implement LivingLabs in the C2B2 case study areas.

The C2B2 LivingLabs methodology for co-creating participatory ocean governance and adaptive management is based on validated approaches of previous implementations of LivingLabs for environmental governance challenges (e.g. Ground Truth 2.0, MICS, MAR2PROTECT) and grounded in social-ecological systems and social learning. It will be applied and validated in the LLs in the three C2B2 case studies, allowing for differences in local contexts, culture, stakeholder relations and other social issues to be taken into account.

This LL methodology is triggered by the need to foster a more resilient and sustainable social-ecological marine system and blue economy in Sweden. The core goals of the C2B2 LLs methodology and approach and all C2B2 LLs-related activities are to:

- (1) engage relevant actors across multiple sectors and governance levels operating in marine environments and interested in marine spatial planning in the C2B2 LLs;
- (2) enhance social learning among all actors involved in the C2B2 LLs, within the organizations to which they belong and at the institutional setting in which they operate; and, thus,
- (3) bring about transformative change towards a more participatory ocean governance and adaptive management across multiple governance levels and blue economy sectors in Sweden, supported by relevant and insightful data and knowledge.

Overall, the C2B2 LL methodology comprises the following:

- Overarching **guiding principles** to guide the implementation of the C2B2 LLs
- Stipulations for the type of **core stakeholders** to be engaged in the LLs

- **Key stages** for setting up and implementing LLs, with a generic list of activities and envisaged outcomes per stage; based on content, process and context dimensions that enable transformative learning to occur among all involved actors and across multiple blue economy sectors and governance levels; namely *Prepare, Form, Explore, Embed, and Evaluate & Sustain*. All of these 5 Stages interact with other C2B2 WPs, and are directed to achieving specific outcomes towards enabling transformative learning and fostering transformative change for more participatory ocean governance and a sustainable blue economy in Sweden.
- A **compendium** with a collection of instructions, worksheets and guidelines that accompanies the C2B2 LL teams in their ‘journey’ throughout each stage of setting up and implementing the C2B2 LLs. This generic Compendium will be used and completed by each C2B2 LL team, serving also as a confidential workspace.
- **Dedicated LL teams of C2B2 partners per case study**, their regular interactions and structured meetings, with mentoring and coaching activities on how to implement the activities of each stage, using the guidance in the compendium.

It is important to note that the implementation of the C2B2 LL methodology by the C2B2 cases is not reliant upon reading this report, nor will this be sufficient. As per C2B2 programme planning, the C2B2 partners will benefit from dedicated training on the C2B2 LL methodology and continued coaching in the C2B2 teams per case study.

This report is structured into 2 Parts. **Part 1** presents the broader context for transformative change in ocean governance of the off-shore environment, the context, rationale and conceptual grounding for the initial C2B2 methodology; the resulting C2B2 LL methodology for co-creating participatory ocean governance in LivingLabs enhanced by state of the art insights from the social learning literature; and how this methodology will be implemented in the C2B2 case studies.

Part 2 of this report presents the prototype compendium. This compendium will be used by the C2B2 LL teams and applied to each of the three C2B2 case studies. It will guide the completion of each stage of the C2B2 LL methodology which, from the *Prepare* to the *Evaluate and Sustain Stage*, will inform the setting up and implementation of the three LLs. This will be accompanied by mentoring of IHE Delft staff and other C2B2 partners with experience in participatory co-creation methods.

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Acronym list

Item	Description
Mistra	Swedish foundation for strategic environmental research
C2B2	Co-creating Better Blue
WP	Work Package
LL/LLs	LivingLab(s)
WE	Water Europe
WoLLs	Water-oriented LivingLabs
SES	Socio-ecological systems

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The overarching aim of the Mistra-C2B2 project *Co-creating a better blue* (hereafter, the C2B2 programme, or C2B2) is to foster transformative change towards a more sustainable blue economy and a more inclusive, science-based and cross-sectoral approach to marine resources, by developing participatory and adaptive ocean governance and management in Sweden.

C2B2 aims to achieve this by accomplishing the following interrelated objectives:

- 1) To provide the basis for a continuously evolving knowledge system for science-based ecosystem governance in Sweden by advancing and interlinking (a) ecosystems and climate science, (b) open, data-driven innovation & emerging technology; and (c) governance theory and practice;
- 2) To demonstrate in practice in Living Labs how the transition towards participatory and science-based ecosystem governance of a sustainable blue economy can be achieved, by initiating, developing and embedding co-creation processes as routines for participatory governance, and ensuring that the adaptive management of practices co-designed in the context of the C2B2 project will endure beyond C2B2's lifetime;
- 3) To reshape our relationship with the ocean by instilling new ways of working together, and practicing science-based ecosystem governance, so that more actors and individuals can realise that they have a direct stake in the offshore space.

The work in WP4 *Co-creation of participatory ocean governance in LivingLabs* (hereafter, WP4) primarily serves to achieve the second objective of the C2B2 programme in three case study areas in Sweden (see Figure 1): in the Gulf of Bothnia (i.e. LivingLab North); in the Baltic Sea (i.e. LivingLab Est) and in the Kattegat-Skagerrak region (i.e. LivingLab West).

Figure 1: Geographical location of the LivingLabs in Sweden

Broadly, the C2B2 LLs methodology and the overall work undertaken in WP4 include the provision of the three C2B2 LLs teams with process guidance for setting up and implementing LivingLabs (LLs) in each C2B2 case study area, as part of the bottom up approach of the overall C2B2 methodology (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: The Overall C2B2 methodology (Source: C2B2 programme Part A)

Broadly, the work undertaken in Work Package 4, *Co-creating participatory governance in Living Labs* (hereafter, WP4), consists of three major, interrelated phases of Action Research: (1) *planning* and (2) *acting*, and (3) *monitoring and reflecting* on the implementation of LLs.

Figure 3: Illustration of the role of WP4 tasks in the overall C2B2 Action Research approach

As illustrated in Figure 3, WP 4, Task T4.1 develops a methodology for co-creating participatory ocean governance by using LivingLabs, provided in this report (i.e. *planning*). Tasks T4.2, T4.3, and T4.4 apply the C2B2 LivingLab methodology to set up a LivingLab in each of the three C2B2 case study areas (i.e. *acting*). Task T4.5 enables and fosters peer-learning and capacity development processes with other reference projects dedicated to enhancing participatory ocean governance in Sweden and internationally. Finally, Task T4.6 provides the monitoring and evaluation of the LL-processes and outcomes in the context of the C2B2 project (i.e. *monitoring & reflecting*). This action research cycle continues throughout the entire research process and describes the recursive activities of researchers and/or practitioners', with the overarching goal of creating new and lasting changes to enhance their practices and the conditions under which they practise (Kennis et al., 2014). The reflection phase calls for a pause in the efforts every so often to evaluate the functionality of the original plan and assesses how it can be improved. In this way, action research enhances the relationship between action and learning and ultimately delivers more appropriate, effective, and nuanced solutions. In C2B2, the action research to be conducted is participatory in that C2B2 engages stakeholders in the design and implementation of, and learning, from the C2B2 LivingLab activities. As explained in Figure 3, tasks T4.1-T4.4 help the C2B2 partners and the LivingLab participants in *planning* and *acting*, while tasks T4.5 and T4.6 help with *monitoring and reflecting* and hence contributing to the overall enhancement of C2B2 activities.

The C2B2 LivingLabs methodology presented in this report which will accompany all WP4-related activities, is based on validated approaches during previous implementations of LivingLabs for environmental governance challenges (e.g. Ground Truth 2.0, MICS, MAR2PROTECT), and is grounded in social-ecological systems and social learning theories. In line with the overall C2B2 programme, the C2B2 LLs methodology is triggered by the need to

foster a more resilient and sustainable social-ecological marine system and blue economy in Sweden.

To achieve this, the core goals of the C2B2 LLs methodology presented in this report are to:

- (1) engage relevant actors across multiple sectors and governance levels operating in marine environments and interested in marine spatial planning in the C2B2 LLs;
- (2) enhance social learning among all actors involved in the C2B2 LLs, within the organizations to which they belong and at the institutional setting in which they operate; and, thus,
- (3) bring about transformative change towards a more participatory ocean governance and adaptive management across multiple governance levels and blue economy sectors in Sweden, supported by relevant and insightful data and knowledge.

The C2B2 LLs methodology provided in this report will be applied and validated in the LLs in the three C2B2 case study areas, enabling careful consideration of the differences in local contexts, culture, stakeholder relations and other social issues.

The specific approach of T4.1 consists of an overall LL methodology, a generic compendium, the formation of teams of C2B2 partners per case study, as well as tailored training and continued coaching for the C2B2 partners. Detailed documentation of the implementation of the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology will ensure that attention is paid to generic aspects of the LL implementation process and to the design of customizable templates and protocols that can be re-used in the future. It will also ensure that changes in the assumptions and recommendations are recognized and documented.

Employing a consistent and overall coherent LL methodology (provided by T4.1) for the demonstration activities in all three C2B2 case studies (T4.2.-T4.4) and a complementary approach for the evaluation activities (T4.6) will ensure that the resulting insights can feed into the production of generic guidelines and recommendations on how to transform towards participatory ocean governance and a sustainable blue economy in Sweden using LivingLabs. This will allow the C2B2 approach to be replicated elsewhere.

1.2 Purpose of this report

The purpose of this report is threefold, namely to:

- (1) set out the context, rationale and conceptual grounding for the initial C2B2 methodology for establishing and running the LivingLabs in the C2B2 case studies;
- (2) describe how the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology will be implemented in the C2B2 case studies by the C2B2 teams per case study, with tailored coaching and via the use of a compendium per case; and
- (3) present the initial version of the generic compendium for the early stages of the methodology.

As such, this report is intended as a **reference document** for the C2B2 consortium capturing the scientific basis and rationale of the C2B2 LL methodology as well as practical aspects of its implementation. It may be of interest to the C2B2 partners wishing to understand the background to, and details of the prototype C2B2 LL methodology and aspects of its

implementation, as well as to the Mistra C2B2 Board members, to academic scholars and LivingLabs practitioners wishing to understand the rationale behind the C2B2 LL methodology.

It is important to note that the implementation of the C2B2 LL methodology by the C2B2 cases is not reliant upon reading this report, nor will this be sufficient. As per C2B2 programme planning, the C2B2 partners will benefit from dedicated training on the C2B2 LL methodology and continued coaching in the C2B2 teams per case study.

1.3 Structure of this report

This report is structured into 2 Parts.

Part 1 presents: (1) the conceptual basis of the C2B2 LivingLab methodology (*Part 1, Chapter 1*); (2) an overall overview of the C2B2 LL methodology and procedure for its implementation (*Part 1, Chapter 2*); and, finally, (3) final reflections and considerations for next steps in the C2B2 programme context.

Part 1 Chapter 1 includes:

- (1) a broad reflection on the need for transformative change to achieve participatory and adaptive ocean governance and a sustainable and resilient blue economy in Sweden (*Part 1, Chapter 1, Section 1.1*);
- (2) an overview of the history and evolution of the LivingLabs approach, and its main shortcomings when applied to achieving sustainable environmental governance and adaptive management (*Part 1, Chapter 1, Section 1.2*);
- (3) an overview of the social learning literature, the main conceptual advances achieved in this field, and how these can be used to enhance the LLs approach and render LLs as valuable tools that can support the attainment of participatory ocean governance and adaptive management (*Part 1, Chapter 1, Section 1.3*)

Part 1 Chapter 2 provides an overview of the resulting C2B2 LL methodology for co-creating participatory ocean governance in LivingLabs, as enhanced by integrating the insights from the social learning literature. This includes:

- (1) an introduction providing an overview of the C2B2 LL methodology and main components (*Part 2, Chapter 2, Section 2.1*);
- (2) a description of the guiding principles and core stakeholders for the C2B2 LLs (*Part 2, Chapter 2, Section 2.2*);
- (3) an overview of the Stages of the C2B2 LL methodology (*Part 2, Chapter 2, Section 2.3*);
- (4) an overview of the implementation procedure to be followed in order to set-up and implement the LLs in each C2B2 case study (*Part 2, Chapter 2, Section 2.4*).

Part 2 of this report presents the prototype compendium. This compendium will be used by the C2B2 LL teams and applied to each of the three C2B2 case studies. It will guide the completion of each stage of the C2B2 LL methodology which, from the *Prepare* to the *Evaluate and Sustain Stage*, will inform the setting up and implementation of the three LLs. This will be accompanied by mentoring of IHE Delft staff and other C2B2 partners with experience in participatory co-creation methods.

PART 1

Conceptual basis and overview of the C2B2 LivingLabs Methodology

Chapter 1: Conceptual basis of the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology

1.1 Transformative change in ocean governance for a sustainable blue economy in Sweden

The Mistra C2B2 programme is based on the realisation that there is an urgent need to radically change the way we think and use the ocean, away from a blue growth-based approach and towards a sustainable blue economy (Eikeset et al., 2018; Smallhorn-West et al., 2022). Transformative change broadly refers to a fundamental and profound shift (rather than incremental changes) that brings about significant and lasting changes in various aspects of a system or a society, including in the underlying structures, institutions, behaviours and norms, in order to better solve complex problems and achieve resilience and sustainability (Biermann & Pattberg, 2008; Stirling, 2014).

The C2B2 programme acknowledges that transformative change requires the “proactive steering of societal transformations towards sustainability” (Halbe & Pahl-Wostl, 2019) and, as such, a holistic and comprehensive process that seeks to change existing systems and norms, aiming for a radical shift towards a more sustainable future. C2B2, therefore, understands transformative change as a process that, instead of achieving mere incremental improvements, aims to foster a more profound and lasting paradigm shift towards a more participatory and adaptive approach in current ocean governance and management for achieving a sustainable blue economy and a more sustainable and resilient social-ecological marine system.

C2B2 aims to bring about such a transformative change by co-creating participatory ocean governance in three LivingLabs (LLs) together with the quadruple helix stakeholders (industry, academia, public sector, civil society) in the Northern (Gulf of Bothnia), Eastern (Baltic Sea) and Western (Kattegat-Skagerrak) regions of Sweden (see above). These LLs will be supported by relevant and insightful data and knowledge (see Figure 4), which will provide nature a voice and enable its inclusion as the fifth stakeholder group in the helix (i.e. quintuple helix).

Also, the design and implementation of such LLs in WP4 will benefit from interactions and feedback loops between the other WPs comprising the overall C2B2 programme, including insights from climate and ecosystem science and the ocean governance and management field that will be produced respectively in WP1 and WP3 (see above).

Figure 4: C2B2 concept (Source: C2B2 programme Part A)

Based on this feedback and the overall purpose of the C2B2 programme, the activities in these LLs are addressed to collectively explore, evaluate and suggest likely sustainability pathways to reshape the underlying ocean governance structures (i.e. norms, regulatory frameworks, roles, responsibilities and coordination among institutions), strategies (i.e. institutional, financial, risk management, physical planning and participation strategies set up by policies for planning) and processes (i.e. planning and management arrangements) that contribute to the status quo.

The C2B2 programme also aims to co-create, experiment with and evaluate data-driven innovative approaches, ideas and holistic solutions to tackle the root causes (rather than the symptoms) of unsustainable ocean management and practices in Sweden. By doing so, the LLs will challenge established norms and suggest new ways of governing the Swedish marine social-ecological system, thus fostering a transition towards a more participatory and adaptive ocean governance and management, and a more sustainable blue economy.

Generating participatory ocean governance and adaptive management demands an inclusive and collaborative environment where formal institutions, informal networks and individuals across multiple sectors and government levels can cooperate, learn, co-produce knowledge and build a common vision for sustainable marine management and spatial planning (Folke, 2006; Garmestani & Benson, 2013).

As outlined in the Introduction of this report, participatory ocean governance is intended to be fostered primarily through the activities comprised by C2B2 Work Package 4, Co-creation of participatory ocean governance in LivingLabs (hereafter, WP4). WP4 aims to co-create participatory ocean governance via the activities that will be co-designed, implemented and evaluated in the context of the LLs that will be established in the three C2B2 case study areas. To enable transformative change towards a more participatory and adaptive ocean governance and sustainable blue economy in these regions, the C2B2 LLs should therefore

ensure that the conditions that enable social learning among all involved actors within and across multiple sectors and governance levels are in place. LLs should also ensure that the social learning processes enacted by them will be oriented towards achieving transformative outcomes not only within and among all actors involved in LLs, but also, and especially, within the organizations to which they belong and within the institutional context in which they operate.

To achieve this, the C2B2 LLs activities therefore aim to: (1) engage relevant actors across multiple sectors and governance levels operating in marine environments and interested in marine spatial planning in the C2B2 LLs; (2) enhance social learning among all actors involved in the C2B2 LLs, within the organizations to which they belong and at the institutional setting in which they operate; and, thus, (3) bring about transformative change towards more participatory ocean governance and adaptive management across multiple governance levels and blue economy sectors in Sweden.

For over three decades, LLs have been extensively used to foster participation in technological innovation processes (see sections below). Although over the last decade or so, LLs are being increasingly used in urban and rural contexts to achieve broader sustainability outcomes, there still is paucity of research and best practice on how to use LLs to foster social learning and transformative change for sustainable environmental governance (Wehn et al, 2018). Integrating the conceptual advances achieved in the social learning and environmental governance literature into the methodological and practical advances achieved in the LLs theory and practice will be crucial to make LLs valuable tools to achieve and measure resilience and sustainability outcomes in localities and across multiple governance levels and social-ecological scales.

The C2B2 LLs methodology proposed in this report, therefore, aims to combine the conceptual advances achieved in the social learning and environmental governance fields with the methodological and practical advances achieved in the LLs literature, and develop a comprehensive and systematic approach that will use LLs to achieve, evaluate and monitor social learning and sustainability transformation outcomes in the ocean governance regimes currently governing social-ecological marine systems in the C2B2 case study areas.

In *Section 1.2* below, we therefore introduce:

1. the LL concept, approach and methodology;
2. how this approach and methodology evolved over the last decades, including how LLs have been recently applied to the environmental governance, in the water sector in general, and for ocean governance in particular;
3. the common characteristics of LLs in terms of their structure, function, processes, and desired outcomes; and
4. the potential and limitations of traditional LL approaches in terms of enhancing social learning and achieving a participatory and adaptive environmental governance.

In *Section 1.3*, we then:

- (1) elaborate on the concept of social learning and how it is commonly defined and applied to the sustainable environmental governance discourse;

- (2) disentangle the key dynamics and dimensions that enable social learning to occur within and across multiple sectors and governance levels;
- (3) discuss social and institutional learning outcomes and their relevance from a sustainable environmental governance perspective; and
- (4) highlight how social learning outcomes may differ in terms of depth, scope, scale and transformative potential.

In Section 1.3.3 (Part 1) of this report, we therefore briefly explain how these conceptual advances inform the C2B2 LL methodology provided.

1.2 LivingLabs

“LivingLabs are about bringing people together to innovate” (Evans, 2019)

LivingLabs (LLs) can be broadly defined as societal arenas (virtual or physical) that bring together a range of stakeholders coming from multiple sectors (e.g. universities, industries, national and local authorities, NGOs and wider civil society) to collaborate in the co-creation, prototyping, validating and testing of complex solutions to real-life problems (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012; Hossain et al., 2019; Luján Soto et al., 2021).

The use of LivingLabs has evolved over time, broadening in aim and scope, with LLs nowadays being applied for a wide range of societal objectives (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012). Although used in a wide range of contexts, LLs maintain certain characteristics that can be considered common features of the various LLs being studied in the literature (Beaudoin et al., 2022; Hossain et al., 2019; McLoughlin et al., 2018) and are disentangled below (see *Part 1, Sub-Section 1.2.3*).

More recently, LLs are being used in the context of environmental governance and spatial planning, with their methodology and approach gaining currency in the water sector in general (Marrades et al., 2021; Ruiz-Ocampo et al., 2023; Willems et al., 2023) and in the ocean governance field, in particular (Franke et al., 2023). This makes the Living Lab approach and methodology particularly relevant for the purposes of the C2B2 programme.

1.2.1 History and evolution of the LivingLabs approach

Scientific foundations of LLs stem from innovation studies in which LLs were used primarily to foster collaboration with the objective to take research and development out of laboratory settings, co-design and develop human-centric Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and test them in real life contexts, through user-driven design methodologies (Von Hippel, 1988). However, over the last three decades, use of LLs has evolved both in aim and scope.

From being primarily used, in the 1990s, to facilitate innovation in physical and/or digital technological products (Abowd, 1999; Abu-Hakima et al., 1998; Lasher et al., 1991) over the last two decades, LLs begun to be used to achieve broader social innovation outcomes. Social innovation outcomes can be broadly understood as “new solutions and instruments to cope with the economic crisis and other global dilemmas such as climate change, energy and

resource scarcity, health and demographic imbalances, which are becoming more urgent and require rapid resolution” (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012, p. 673).

As such, social innovation outcomes do not simply refer to ‘all things social’ as opposed to technological innovation; rather, social innovation outcomes stress that the focus of the innovation process is on addressing societal challenges or unsatisfied collective needs, and in doing so, includes involving technological innovation along with essential changes in social practices (Wehn et al., 2021).

In Europe, LLs emerged around the 1990s and gained visibility with the establishment of the European Network of LivingLabs (ENoLL), which was founded in November 2006, under the Finnish Presidency of the Council of the European Union (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012). This network gathered, over the years, the membership of 460 LLs, and it currently comprises over 165 LLs around the world, including federations of LLs like the Africa Network of LLs (ANoLL), the China Network of LLs (CNoLL) and the Brazil Network of LLs (BNoLL), and collaboration with, among others, the World Bank, the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), and the Europe Business Network (EBN) (ENoLL website).

The practitioners’ definition of LLs provided by ENoLL conceives LivingLabs as it follows:

Open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations and businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders (*What are Living Labs*, n.a.).

Since 2006, and arguably prompted by the establishment of ENoLL, the publication of scholarly articles about LivingLabs has grown considerably (Hossain et al., 2019), together with the number of projects and case studies that made use of the LLs approach and methodology. Nowadays, the pervasiveness of LLs is evidenced not only by the growing number of ENoLL’s members and partner organizations adhering to the network across the globe, but also by a growing literature investigating the characteristics, functions and outcomes of LLs as applied to a variety of sectors and research fields.

This literature includes LLs-related research in: Agriculture and land-related ecosystem services (Bouwma et al., 2022; Luján Soto et al., 2021; McPhee et al., 2021)); university campuses and higher education (Barakabitze et al., 2019; Gomez & Derr, 2021; Polin et al., 2024; van den Heuvel et al., 2021; Zen, 2017) healthcare and quality of life (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012; Korman et al., 2016); sustainable governance and sustainability transition in cities (Bulkeley et al., 2016; Nevens et al., 2013; Voytenko et al., 2016) as well as in rural areas (Berberi et al., 2023; Guzman et al., 2008; Luján Soto et al., 2021); and water governance and management (Alamanos et al., 2022; Marrades et al., 2021; Ruiz-Ocampo et al., 2023) including ocean governance and marine spatial planning (Franke et al., 2023).

1.2.2 LivingLabs in environmental governance, the water sector and marine environments

Over the last two decades, as shown by the variety of LL configurations that have been identified in the LL literature (see Table 1 below), LLs have been increasingly used as approaches for achieving broader place-based sustainable development outcomes in urban and rural settings (Gascó, 2017; Kronsell & Mukhtar-Landgren, 2018; Nevens et al., 2013; Reiter

et al., 2014; Willems et al., 2023). Moving beyond their traditional application to the innovation and ICT fields, LLs, therefore, have been increasingly used in the context of policy and the public sector (Gascó, 2017; Kronsell & Mukhtar-Landgren, 2018; Taylor, 2021; Willems et al., 2023) and of environmental governance, both in urban (Claude et al., 2017; Voytenko et al., 2016) and in rural areas (Beaudoin et al., 2022; Berberi et al., 2023; Fèche et al., 2021; Guzman et al., 2008; Luján Soto et al., 2021) with the specific objective to foster social learning among all involved actors to enable sustainability transformation in governance and planning.

Table 1: Illustration of LivingLab types & terminology (not based on comprehensive review) source: (Howaldt et al., 2019)

Living Lab types	Other related terms that sometimes refer to LL configurations/structures	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blue Living Lab Circular Living Lab City Living Lab Co-creation Living Lab Corporate (social) Living Lab Design Living Lab Digital Living Lab e-Living Lab Fab Living Lab Green Living Lab IoT Living Lab Living innovation platform Living Laboratory Living Laboratory for Sustainability Open Innovation Living Lab Open Living Lab Rural Living Lab Silver Living Lab Sustainable Living Lab Test-bed Transition Living Lab University Living Lab Urban Living Lab 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blue Lab Change Lab Centre for Innovation Circular Lab Circular Talent Lab City Lab Civic Lab Co-creation hub Co-creation Lab Co-design Lab Co-Lab Community Lab Corporate Social Innovation Lab Corporate Social Lab Coworking space Design Lab Do-tank Fab-Lab Governance Lab Hackers space Hive Hub Impact hub 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Innovation Lab Policy Lab Public and Social Innovation Lab (PSI) Public Lab Sandbox Social cluster Social hub Social Impact hub Social innovation Lab Social Innovation Park Social innovation platform Social Lab Societal pilot Social Space for Research & Innovation (SSRI) Rural Lab Social Science Park Tech-Lab Transition Lab Urban Lab Other

With community participation and stakeholder engagement becoming increasingly recognised as crucial for the achievement of long-term benefits in water-related projects (Wehn et al., 2020). LivingLabs are gaining currency in water management practice too (Alamanos et al., 2022; Marrades et al., 2021; Rosenberger et al., 2021; Ruiz-Ocampo et al., 2023; Willems et al., 2023). The popularity gained by the most recent application of the LL methodology and approach to the water sector has resulted into Water Europe (WE) coining the term “Water-oriented LivingLabs” (WoLLs) to indicate those LLs specifically addressed to enhance innovation in water management. Initiated in 2004 by the European Commission, in 2007, WE became a member-based platform whose aim is to represent the whole value chain of water, and achieve a ‘water smart society’. As envisioned by WE, a water smart society is a society in which “the true value of water is recognised and realised, and all available water sources are managed in such a way that water scarcity and pollution of water are avoided” (Atlas of the EU Water-Oriented Living Labs 2019).

There are over 80 WoLLs across Europe that joined the WE network so far (*Atlas of the EU Water-Oriented Living Labs 2019*). WE has a specific technology innovation-driven approach to LLs, and hence WoLLs primarily relate to the traditional understanding of LLs, considering LL as tools that enable the prototyping, testing and evaluation of new technologies for water management and treatment, primarily addressed to prevent and/or mitigate pollution, advance circular water solutions and foster climate adaptation (*Atlas of the EU Water-Oriented Living Labs 2019*).

In general, most WoLLs pertain to water management and subsequent technologies for improving the quantity and quality of freshwater, water production, distribution and (re)use. Thus far, only a few WoLLs are concerned with achieving sustainable water governance, and most of them do not differ too much from traditional LLs in their early application (see Box 1).

Box 1: LivingLabs in the water sector (Water-oriented LivingLabs, WoLLs)

Definition of WoLLs (*Atlas of the EU Water-Oriented Living Labs 2019, p. 3*)

“Water-Oriented, real-life demonstration and implementation instrument that brings together public and private institutions, government, civil society, and academia to jointly build structured grounds to develop, validate, and scale-up innovations that embrace new technologies, governance, business models, and advancing innovative policies to achieve a Water-Smart Society”.

General WoLLs characteristics (*Atlas of the EU Water-Oriented Living Labs 2019, p. 8*)

- Demo-type and platform-type research and innovation settings, with context-specific needs and enabling conditions
- Water-oriented interventions with a cross-sector nexus approach in real-world and/or realistic environments
- Proactive learning and innovation ecosystem with R&D continuity and reproducibility
- Open and local multi-stakeholder governance structure with democratic control systems

Limitations of WoLLs Water Europe (Adapted from Water Europe, 2019, p.8)

- Lack of standardization in organizing user involvement.
- Collaboration is limited to users in urban areas, not with communities.
- Operating on a project basis, without involving prolonged engagement with communities
- Operational difficulties, i.e. network efficiency, sustainability, engagement with diversified community of users, fragmented service providers.

While C2B2 is certainly not the first endeavour into the water and LivingLabs arena, it is one of a few that deal specifically with ocean governance. Very few LivingLabs sit squarely at the intersection of ocean waters and governance (Franke et al., 2023), some of which are reported and described here below (see Box 2).

Box 2: Examples of LivingLabs in marine environments

The Sea project (Sweden)

This project started in 2017 and it is still ongoing. It is led (and founded) by the Åbo Akademi University with the support of the Academy of Finland. The project at large is “a Living Lab for marine and maritime research with a focus on coastal and marginal seas” [The Sea - A Living Lab | Åbo Akademi University \(abo.fi\)](#)

The WhiteFishMaLL (North Atlantic Whitefish Marine Living Lab)

This project ran from 2011 to 2014 in the UK. The project aimed to create a successful branding campaign for whitefish from the North Atlantic in regard to sustainability and consumer benefits. However, a second major goal of the project was “to demonstrate how to establish Living Lab methodology in the marine sector”. The ultimate outcome of this LivingLab was an online platform with information on the fish and about the specific product batch. [WhiteFishMaLL \(North Atlantic Whitefish Marine Living Lab\) | Nordic Innovation](#)

The Rijeka LivingLab (Croatia)

This project is a hub of four LivingLabs in Croatia, one of which is the *Maritime Navigation Safety and Security* Lab. This lab focuses on the safety and security of people travelling and transporting goods on the ocean. They work on issues of communication both through a technological lens and a cooperation lens among stakeholders, including authorities in Croatia, Slovenia, and Italy. ([LivingLabs - European Network of LivingLabsEuropean Network of LivingLabs \(enoll.org\)](#))

Eckernförder Bucht 2030 (Bay of Kiel, Germany):

This projects works to develop a more sustainable utilization of the Bay of Kiel through the use of a LivingLab. By bringing together stakeholders from agriculture, fisheries, tourism, municipalities, navy, and sports sectors, the project hopes to, among other things, successfully implement the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive. This project uses a LivingLab to directly engage and with and improve policy implementation. [Living Lab Eckernförder Bucht 2030 \(oceanandsociety.org\)](#)

Gute Küste Niedersachsen (‘Good Coast Lower Saxony’, Germany)

This 5 year-long project started in 2020 aims to enhance coastal protections that strengthens ecosystems in the Lower Saxony North Sea coast. The project uses “real-world labs” to co-design and execute research on multi-functional coastal protection measures long-term functionality.

[Making the UN Ocean Decade work? The potential for, and challenges of, transdisciplinary research and real-world laboratories for building towards ocean solutions - Franke - 2023 - People and Nature - Wiley Online Library](#)

The Inno-port Scheveningen Port LL (The Netherlands):

The LivingLab is the test site for the Ocean Clean-up Project and is dedicated to improving innovations in coastal zones and water management. It involves municipal actors and entrepreneurs and works on improving the spatial development innovations with the end goal of marketing the designs.

[Atlas-of-the-EU-Water-Oriented-Living-Labs.pdf \(watereurope.eu\)](#)

The Holwerd aan Zee LL (Wadden Sea, The Netherlands)

This LivingLab is unique in its centering of students from MBO, HBO and WO who work together with governments, citizens, entrepreneurs, environmental organizations and knowledge institutions. The LivingLab focuses on developing the Wadden coast in collaborative ways that using and creating a truly multidisciplinary environment that bring together nature, technology, culture, history, and art. [Living Lab - Holwerd aan Zee](#)

Delta Plan for Biodiversity Restoration (The Netherlands)

The Delta Plan for Biodiversity Restoration is a partnership among over 90 public and private organizations. It runs the coastal LL B7 and aims to establish LLs standards which can be representatives of all landscapes in coastal and marine environments. [Delta Plan for Biodiversity Recovery | Naturalis](#)

The BRIDGE-BS project (Black Sea)

This project draws on marine research and innovation and is addressed to co-develop Blue Economy pathways for the sustainable utilization of the Black Sea’s ecosystem services. Five LLs covering the Romanian, Bulgarian and Georgian Black Sea coastline and marine space as well as two Turkish regions (Istanbul/Bosporus and Sinup) are being implemented. In the BRIDGE_BS context, LLs represent “an instrument to empower local communities in the future sustainable management of the Black Sea, breaking sectoral silos and ensuring a systemic approach”. [BRIDGE-BS | European Marine Board](#)

1.2.3 LivingLabs structure, function, processes, desired outcomes

Beyond the wide range of diverse contexts in which LLs have been used so far, the LLs literature has converged towards identifying common features characterizing all LLs, independently from their context of application (Beaudoin et al., 2022; Hossain et al., 2019; McLoughlin et al., 2018; Voytenko et al., 2016; Westerlund et al., 2018).

Concerning the LLs in ENOLL, a key element that these LLs have in common is the role that they play as bridging entities, intermediaries and/or orchestrators among citizens, research organisations, companies and government agencies. Other common characteristics include:

1. **Active stakeholder involvement** (i.e. empowering stakeholders to influence innovation processes);
2. **Real-life setting** (i.e. testing and experimenting new technologies in real-life contexts);
3. **Multi-stakeholder participation** (i.e. involving technology providers, service providers, relevant institutional actors, professional or residential stakeholders);
4. **Multi-method approach** (i.e. combining methods and tools from different disciplines, including ethnography, psychology, sociology, strategic management, engineering);
5. **Co-creation** (i.e. enabling iterations of design cycles with different sets of stakeholders);
6. **Orchestration** (i.e. enabling coordination and collaboration among stakeholders coming from different sectors, epistemologies and worldviews).

Beyond ENOLL's approach, the features that the LLs literature has identified as common characteristics of all LLs can be summarized into four key dimensions: **LL function**, **LL structure**, **the processes** in which LLs are grounded and which they should enact; and the desired **outcomes** on which LLs are focused. All LLs, especially those designed and implemented during the last decade or so, can be considered as place-based and participants-centred open innovation ecosystems that are:

- (1) experimentation and learning-centred;
- (2) participation-based and co-creation oriented; and
- (3) focused on (social) innovation and broader social-ecological resilience and sustainability outcomes.

In each of these key LLs dimensions, there are specific characteristics that are common to any LL. These characteristics are reflected in the overall C2B2 LLs methodology and in the C2B2 LL Compendium (see Part 2), which will enable C2B2 LL teams to carefully take them into account when designing and setting up the LLs in the C2B2 case study area.

Beyond the variety of contexts to which they have been applied so far, all LLs have two primary **functions**: (1) to enable experimentation in real-life contexts and (2) facilitate recursive social learning among all actors involved.

As place-based, participant-centred innovation ecosystems, LLs should facilitate experiments of new visions, ideas, technologies, projects, plans, policies and norms under real world conditions and in highly visible ways, something that can prompt transformative change at local level and facilitate such change to be scaled-up on a higher level (Baccarne et al., 2014; Voytenko et al., 2016).

LLs also have the function to facilitate iterative and recursive social learning processes. These social learning processes should enable among all involved actors – within the organizations to which they belong, and across multiple governance levels – collective learning about: (1) each other's perspectives, understandings and worldviews; (2) the common problem and needs that should be addressed; (3) the kind of experimentation that should be tested and validated; (4) the outcomes of such testing and validation; and (5) the lessons that can be drawn from such outcomes. To make them accomplish these functions, a LL should be based on a specific structure, enact adequate social processes, and be oriented towards consistent outcomes.

LLs can be physical or virtual, and based on material and/or immaterial infrastructure (Schoorman et al., 2013), however, their **structure**, meaning the set of rules, roles and responsibilities that regulate coordination and action in a LL context, should enable the development of an open and inclusive innovation ecosystem. This structure should therefore make sure that coordination and action in LLs are: (1) geographically embedded in real places; (2) based on the inputs gained from the participants; and (3) directed towards territorializing social innovation in specific regions (or social areas of influence) at a more manageable scale (Voytenko et al., 2016). Furthermore, their structure should enable divergent perspectives to be equally considered and valued, maintaining a balance among all disciplines, sectors and actors involved, ensuring that one does not outweigh another.

Furthermore, all social processes enacted by any LL, by definition, should be **participatory processes**. These processes should be grounded in a specific code of conduct for participants and enable constructive interaction, knowledge integration, mutual learning, inclusion and equity. They should be addressed to facilitate knowledge co-production among all actors involved about: (1) the common problems and associated needs to be addressed; (2) the common vision and desired outcomes to be achieved; and (3) the kind of experiment to be conducted in order to address such problems and achieve such outcomes. In this vein, being based on, and enacting effective participatory processes is a common characteristic of any LL, and this is therefore crucial for LLs to effectively facilitate experimentation and social learning among all involved stakeholders.

Finally, if in the early 1990s, LLs were primarily addressed to developing and testing new technologies and bring about user-driven innovations in the ICT sector, nowadays most LLs aim to achieve broader **resilience and sustainability outcomes** both in the places where they are embedded, and across multiple governance levels and broader social-ecological scales, through creating positive spillover effects (Bulkeley & Castán Broto, 2013; Voytenko et al., 2016).

1.2.4 Main shortcomings of the LivingLabs approach

Although there is a broad consensus about the common characteristics and functions of LLs, there are still gaps and shortcomings regarding their effective implementation. There is still paucity of research concerning the enabling dynamics and dimensions of social learning that LLs should put in place to ensure that such learning occurs. There is also little scientific analysis that disentangles the different social learning outcomes that can be achieved in the context of LLs and how these outcomes may differ in terms of depth, width, scope and transformative potential. Research on LLs still remains vague in terms of the social learning outcomes that LLs can achieve, the transformative changes that they can trigger and the sustainability transformations that they can foster, especially from a resilience, sustainability and sustainable environmental governance perspective. As we could also see with WoLLs, there still is a lack of guidance for their design, implementation and evaluation.

Such limitations and shortcomings in LLs theory and practice are common to most research concerned with public participation. It has been widely recognized that collective self-reflection through interaction and dialogue among actors (Pahl-Wostl, 2009), multi-stakeholder engagement, concerted action and other participatory processes are enabling conditions for social learning to occur (Wehn et al., 2020). However, it cannot be assumed that such participatory processes inevitably lead to social learning (Bull et al., 2008; Reed et al., 2010). Social learning indeed has often been confused with the conditions and methods that enable it to occur, with many projects claiming to be social learning projects, while rarely going beyond simply facilitating stakeholder participation processes, thus providing little or no evidence of the social learning being facilitated, and/or remaining little explicit about any attempt to measure the social learning outcomes achieved (Reed et al., 2010; Wehn et al., 2020).

The combined result of these theoretical and practical gaps in the LLs literature is that there still is little understanding of how LLs should enable the creation of a common vision and lead to the establishment of social learning agendas. Also, there still is little understanding of: (1) the social learning outcomes that LLs create at the individual, social-relational, organizational and institutional levels; (2) the sustainability transformations and broader impacts they create on the social-ecological system under consideration in terms of resilience and sustainability; and (3) how to monitor, evaluate and assess (and learn from) these specific social learning LLs outcomes and broader LLs impacts (Ballon et al., 2018; Bouwma et al., 2022; Bronson et al., 2021; Van Geenhuizen, 2018).

With LLs gaining currency in the broader governance and planning discourses, and with LLs increasingly used in urban and rural settings, as the new mantra for sustainable development, there is an urgent need to fill these theoretical and practical gaps and strengthen the LLs approach with key insights from the social learning literature. In the subsection below, we define social learning, and disentangle its key enabling dynamics and dimensions, and its range of outcomes. We then illustrate how the conceptual advances related to social learning can fruitfully inform an innovative LL approach to and methodology for sustainable environmental governance, the C2B2 LL methodology. Further implementing and testing this methodology in the context of C2B2 WP4 (see above) can help fill these theoretical and practical shortcomings of the LLs approach and implementation, and make LLs valuable tools to achieve sustainable environmental governance in Sweden and beyond.

1.3 Social learning for participatory and adaptive ocean governance

“Ultimately situations such as water governing and climate change adapting are problems of relationship – of human beings with the biosphere”(Ison et al., 2015, p. 105).

Social learning broadly refers to any change in understanding that takes place in the individuals involved and goes beyond the individuals to become situated within wider social units or communities of practice within society (Reed et al., 2010). As a process that occurs in society, social learning is directed towards achieving specific outcomes and triggered by specific social conditions. The outcomes of social learning processes are the changes in understanding that occur both at the individual level, and at a broader social scale through wider social interactions.

These changes can occur at surface level and include acquiring new knowledge and skills through learning about the consequences of an action (i.e. *single-loop learning*). They can also occur at deeper cognitive level and be the result of what is understood as *multi-loop learning* (i.e. double and triple-loop learning) or *transformative learning* (Anand et al., 2020; Hoggan & Kasl, 2023; Imperiale & Vanclay, 2023a, 2023b; Kasl & Elias, 1997; Mezirow, 1991; Owen & Buck, 2020; Prutzer et al., 2021) thus leading to more radical changes in feelings, attitudes, actions, behaviours and social norms, through reflection on: (1) the assumptions that underpin action (i.e. *double-loop learning outcomes*); and (2) the higher-level values and norms that subtend such assumptions (i.e. *triple-loop learning outcomes*). The implications of single-loop and transformative learning (i.e. double and triple-loop learning) for environmental governance and for the required transformative changes to achieve participatory and adaptive environmental governance are discussed in sub-section 2.2.3 below (see Figure 5 below).

In the environmental governance discourse, social learning is considered as being a key process for any transformative change in environmental governance regimes aiming to enhance the resilience and sustainability of social-ecological systems (SESs) and the sustainable governance and management of natural resources within such systems (Garmestani & Benson, 2013; Imperiale & Vanclay, 2021; Järnberg et al., 2023; Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Westley, 2013). According to SES theory, the resilience of a system is not determined by the capacity of larger and slower levels of organization (e.g., cities, network of municipalities) to control change driven by disturbances (in systems that are assumed to be stable), but rather by their ability to: (1) be sensitive to, learn from, include, and strengthen the capacities of smaller sub-systems (e.g., neighbourhoods; rural villages) to learn from disturbances and transform in order to better cope with such disturbances in localities, and (2) scale-up such social learning and sustainability transformation processes across multiple sectors, government levels and wider social-ecological scales (Armitage et al., 2012; Armitage et al., 2009; Beratan, 2007; Berkes & Ross, 2013; Cox, 2016; Davidson, 2010; Folke, 2006; Garmestani & Benson, 2013; Imperiale & Vanclay, 2021; Robertson et al., 2021).

Along with the growing realisation in policy and science that transformative change in general, and sustainability transformations in particular, are place-based, increasing attention is being paid to social learning as a means to conceptualize and drive such change in localities, and to scale-up it across multiple governance levels (Wehn et al., 2020).

Social learning can thus be considered a process that can enable multi-level, cross-sectoral and cross-scalar governance adaptation, and is therefore key for governance regimes to become adaptive and capable of coping with continuously changing environments, especially in the face of anthropogenic pressures and other disturbances characterizing the global risk landscape in which we live (Armitage et al., 2008; Garmestani & Benson, 2013; Imperiale & Vanclay, 2021, 2023a; Ovink et al., 2023; Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Wehn et al., 2020).

1.3.1 Dynamics, dimensions, enabling and hindering factors of social learning in SES governance

A wide literature (Ernst, 2019; Keen et al., 2005; O'Toole, 2004) has discussed the enabling conditions for social learning processes to occur in environmental governance regimes. Broadly speaking, three basic, nested and inter-level dynamics enable social learning to occur in governance regimes, thus leading to adaptive governance and resilience-building across multiple governance levels and social-ecological scales: horizontal interactions, upwards integrations and downward regulations (Berkes, 2009; Berkes & Ross, 2013, 2016; Imperiale & Vanclay, 2021; Medema et al., 2014).

Horizontal interactions enable social learning to occur among stakeholders at the same governance level. **Upwards integrations** enable interactions and social learning to occur among actors at multiple governance levels and facilitate lower-level social learning outcomes to be integrated and scaled-up across wider social-ecological scales. **Downward regulations** enable recursive social learning among actors across multiple governance levels that strengthen both horizontal interactions and upwards integrations in a continuous process of collaborative problem-solving, ultimately leading to multi-level adaptive governance and co-management approaches (see Figure 4).

Figure 5: Enabling social learning (and building resilience) at all levels of social-ecological governance.

Source: Imperiale and Vanclay (2021)

To make these three social learning dynamics happen, and therefore create adaptive governance regimes, there are four key cross-cutting dimensions to consider:

- (1) **the content** (i.e. *learning what and why?*);
- (2) **the process** (i.e. *learning how?*);
- (3) **the internal context** (i.e. *learning by whom and in which organizational setting?*); and
- (4) **the external context** (i.e. *learning in the face of what external challenges and opportunities?*).

The content dimension comprises the activities that lead to the scoping of the (set of) problem(s) or issues, and the identification of the desired outcomes for which social learning and transformative change are considered worthwhile. **The process dimension** comprises the multi-level, cross-sectoral, and cross-scalar dynamics through which: (1) the problems and associated needs – to be scoped and addressed –, and the desired outcomes – to be achieved – are shared among actors within and across multiple governance levels; (2) a learning agenda and associated rules, roles and responsibilities are negotiated; and (3) a common vision about the problems, desired outcomes, and concerted actions needed to address these problems and achieve these outcomes is developed. **The internal context dimension** refers to those pre-existing organizational conditions and individual attitudes that characterise the internal environment of a governance system and influence the effectiveness of social learning in such system. Finally, **the external context dimension** refers to the external environment on which a governance system has little influence and by which social learning may be triggered or undermined.

As identified in the environmental governance literature (Keen et al., 2005), there are enabling and hindering factors that run along these three dynamics and cut across these four dimensions and can contribute to (or undermine) social learning across multiple sectors and governance levels. In the content dimension, the framing and scoping of the problems and the identification of the desired outcomes should be system-oriented and enable systems thinking capable of understanding coupled social-ecological interactions (i.e. **enabling content factors**). They should result from a collective self-reflection surrounding: (1) the status quo of the governance (strategies, processes and structures) of the social-ecological system under consideration; (2) the conditions of the natural resources within such system; and (3) main related past, current and future human activities.

Such framing and scoping of the problems and identification of the desired outcomes should be the result of meaningful integration of the perspectives of all involved actors, across sectors and multiple governance levels. These actors come from different backgrounds and have different interests, epistemologies and worldviews. It is therefore important that the framing and scoping of the issues, and the identification of the desired outcomes would reflect such diversity, while, at the same time identify common problems that affect everyone and their respective interests.

Furthermore, since social learning is an iterative and recursive process – (ideally) evolving from single to multiple-loops, and, thus, widening in depth, scope, scale and transformative potential – its content dimension, should not only relate to the framing and scoping of the problems to be addressed and the desired outcomes to be achieved. It should also relate to the identification of the shared change strategies and co-management activities needed to

address such problems and achieve such outcomes, and to the continuous co-monitoring, review and assessment of the change strategies and concerted activities to be implemented against the agreed outcomes.

There are process factors, as well as internal and external context factors, that enable such a collective self-reflection to take place and the multiple perspectives to be integrated content-wise. **Enabling process factors** include the design and implementation of participatory processes to create inclusive knowledge systems:

1. involving multiple actors coming from different sectors and governance levels (*multi-stakeholder engagement*);
2. sharing knowledge and integrating local knowledge with government science, academic science and other different epistemologies and worldviews (i.e. *transdisciplinarity*);
3. co-creating new transdisciplinary knowledge (i.e. *knowledge co-production*); and, therefore,
4. developing a common vision of the problem(s) to be addressed, the outcomes to be achieved and the shared change strategies and concerted actions to be implemented (i.e. *convergence of goals*).

More generally, such participatory processes should provide an enabling and democratic environment characterized by open discourse based on principles and rules of dialogue (Allwood et al., 2000; Bohm, 1996; Brown & Danaher, 2019; Murray, 2010), ultimately leading to building trust, mutual understanding, and mutual learning and agreement among all involved actors, across sectors and multiple governance levels (Imperiale & Vanclay, 2021; Medema et al., 2014).

Enabling internal factors that can facilitate such participatory processes and therefore contribute to multiple-loop social learning among actors across multiple sectors and governance levels relate to both individual attitudes and organizational settings. The former refers to the characteristics and attitudes of the actors being engaged, which facilitate social learning processes and include: tolerance of ambiguity; flexibility and open-mindedness; technical and social competences; awareness of sustainability issues; capability for critical self-reflection; commitment to share knowledge and learn; reliability; consistency and respectfulness towards other peoples' feelings and perspectives.

The latter refers to pre-existing internal organizational and institutional settings characterizing the governance regime in which social learning processes take place. These include horizontal and vertical mechanisms that enable multi-level institutional interplay and collaboration, including:

- two-way feedback mechanisms between government policy and local institutions;
- networked governance mechanisms;
- innovative institutional structures and partnerships committed to ongoing multiple-loop and transformative learning; and
- other vertical and horizontal institutional and informal mechanisms and entities.

These mechanisms and entities should be committed to fostering social learning, and to enabling the sharing of knowledge, information, power, responsibility, technology and resources for shared decision-making and co-management across multiple governance levels.

Finally, **enabling external factors** that can trigger social learning processes include crises events, which can turn into windows of opportunity to foster institutional learning and transformative change, political support and buy-in, supportive regulatory frameworks and funding instruments at national and regional levels.

Conversely, lack of such enabling factors in the content, process and context dimensions, and in the internal and external contexts, seriously undermines any attempt of fostering effective social learning and achieving transformative change across multiple sectors and governance levels. Broadly speaking, the hindering factors primarily relate to lack of funding, time and external support, and to top-down command-and-control governance strategies and techno-scientific knowledge. These, together, undermine the inclusion and integration of different epistemologies and worldviews and the building of transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes; the design and implementation of effective participatory strategies and the developing of a common vision and a co-management approach; and the coordination and sharing of knowledge, information, technologies, power, responsibilities and resources needed to co-design and implement co-management activities, and collectively, monitor, reflect on and assess such activities.

1.3.2 Outcomes of social learning processes in adaptive and participatory governance contexts

Understanding the dynamics, dimensions and the enabling and hindering factors of social learning is necessary but not sufficient to operationalise social learning, and therefore, monitor, measure and evaluate the effectiveness of social learning processes. For an efficient implementation and concurrent evaluation of such processes, it is therefore important to understand how to identify the outcomes of social learning. This is especially important for the applied setting of the C2B2 programme, which employs Action Research (plan – act – monitor – reflect, see Figure 3, above) in WP4, which consists in: (1) planning and establishing a consistent methodology for C2B2 LLs implementation (T4.1); (2) carefully implementing the C2B2 LL activities in the three case studies (T4.2-T4.4); while (3) monitoring, measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of social learning processes for transformative change towards a more participatory and adaptive ocean governance and a sustainable blue economy in the C2B2 case studies (in T4.6).

Drawing on the definition of social learning provided by Reed et al. (2010), discussed above, we consider social learning outcomes as follows:

Any change in understanding and in the attitudes, beliefs, values, actions, behaviours and norms that takes place in the individuals involved and goes beyond the individuals to become situated within wider social units, including within the organisations to which these actors belong, and the institutional setting in which they operate.

Changes at the individual level can be:

1. at surface level and triggered by a reflection on actions and experiences, which leads to acquiring new knowledge and skills (i.e. single-loop learning); and

2. at deeper cognitive level, thus triggered by deeper reflections on the assumptions underlying actions (i.e. double-loop learning) and/or on the higher-level values and norms that subtend such assumptions (i.e. triple-loop learning).

Changes that occur at deeper cognitive levels therefore result in changes in individuals' attitudes, actions and behaviours, which are the outcomes at the individual level of what is understood as multiple-loop social learning, or transformative learning processes (Anand et al., 2020; Hoggan & Kasl, 2023; Imperiale & Vanclay, 2023a, 2023b; Kasl & Elias, 1997; Mezirow, 1991; Owen & Buck, 2020; Prutzer et al., 2021; Sterling, 2011).

For social learning to occur, however, it must move beyond fostering cognitive and/or behavioural changes at the individual level and become situated at a broader social scale through wider social interactions and participatory processes. In common social contexts, social learning outcomes should therefore not only be observed at the individual level, but also at social-relational levels, in terms of changes (or improvements) of the social interactions among the actors involved in social learning processes.

Furthermore, as we explained above, in a governance context, social learning is understood as a change process that occurs at individual level and becomes situated not only at a wider social scale in general, but, more specifically, at multiple governance levels, i.e. multi-level and cross-sectoral adaptive governance process that can lead to:

1. *'Fixing errors from routine'*, thus involving the identification of alternative or innovative strategies, tools and actions to resolve specific problems and improve certain outcomes (i.e. single-loop learning outcomes);
2. *'Correcting errors by adjusting values and policies'*, through questioning the underlying values within a policy, and the governance strategies (i.e. the institutional, financial, risk management, physical planning and participation strategies) set up by it (i.e. double-loop learning outcomes); and, finally,
3. *'Correcting errors by re-designing governance, norms and protocols'*, through questioning the existing norms and protocols that orient policies and set-up the regulatory frameworks through which policies establish the governance strategies of natural resources management, ultimately resulting into new norms, new policies, new governance strategies and improved natural resources management approaches and related activities (i.e. triple-loop learning outcomes) (*adapted from Armitage et al., 2008*).

The outcomes of social learning processes in governance regimes should therefore be understood, observed, monitored, measured and evaluated in terms of changes that occur at different:

- *width* (individual/cognitive/behavioural outcomes, social-relational & organisational outcomes, institutional outcomes, and social-ecological outcomes);
- *depth* (i.e. single-loop, double-loop and triple-loop learning outcomes); and
- *direction*, thus across the three dynamics through which social learning processes occur in nested, multi-level governance systems (i.e. horizontal interactions, upwards integrations and downwards regulations).

Social learning outcomes in governance systems at the individual/cognitive/behavioural level can be observed in terms of cognitive and/or behavioural changes. These changes, as explained above, can occur at surface level, resulting in individual acquisition of new knowledge and skills, and at deeper level, thus constituting the outcomes of transformative learning, and therefore resulting in more radical changes in individual's attitudes, beliefs, actions and behaviours towards other people and the environment. These individual/cognitive/behavioural changes can occur within actors operating at the same governance level, and/or within actors operating at *different* governance levels.

Social learning outcomes in governance systems at the social-relational level are improvements in the social interactions among the actors being engaged within and across multiple sectors and governance levels. These improvements should descend from, and – in turn – enhance the transformative changes in individuals' attitudes, actions and behaviours described above, and include the development – where missing – of the social learning's enabling content, process and context factors (see above).

The social learning outcomes in governance systems at the social-relational level can also include other social-relational changes in terms of enhancement, among the actors involved, of: communication; social networks; recognition and understanding of each other's experiences, knowledge and capacities; sense of community and/or group identity; ability to cooperate; understanding of shared problems and needs; and collective capacity to identify shared goals and develop a common vision. These social-relational changes can occur *among* actors operating at the same governance level, and/or *among* actors operating at different governance levels (Medema et al., 2014; Reed et al., 2010).

Social learning outcomes at the institutional level, include:

1. *single-loop institutional learning outcomes*, which descend from collective (cross-sectoral, multi-level and cross-scalar) self-reflection surrounding the question '*are we doing the things right?*', and result into adjustments of current institutional arrangements to integrate new knowledge and adopt innovative technologies;
2. *double-loop institutional learning outcomes*, which descend from collective (cross-sectoral, multi-level and cross-scalar) self-reflection surrounding the question '*are we doing the right thing?*', and result into more complex changes in the policies and governance strategies that orient natural resources management approaches and activities, ultimately leading to collective reconsiderations of existing natural resource management goals and approaches; and
3. *triple-loop institutional learning outcomes*, which descend from collective (cross-sectoral, multi-level and cross-scalar) self-reflection surrounding the questions '*how do we decide what is right and whether we are doing the right thing?*', and result into changes in the norms, regulatory frameworks and protocols that inform the policies and governance strategies of natural resources management and related activities; adapted from (Armitage et al., 2008; Medema et al., 2014; Pahl-Wostl, 2009), see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Illustration of single/double/triple loop institutional learning

Source: Adapted from (Armitage et al., 2008; Medema et al., 2014; Pahl-Wostl, 2009)

Changes at institutional level result from transformative learning at the individual and social-relational levels. However, changes may be in any direction, and/or actors, across multiple sectors and governance levels, can have different goals. Ideally, as we discussed above, the changes prompted by transformative learning should lead the multiple actors to converge towards a common vision and shared goals oriented towards improving natural resource management and social-ecological interactions, thus bringing to enhanced sustainability and resilience of the overall social-ecological system under consideration.

To enable this convergence of goals to happen, it is crucial to design and implement meaningful and innovative participatory processes informed by sustainability science and capable of leading to enhanced shared awareness, among all actors involved in social learning processes within and across multiple governance level, of the common problems and the sustainability and resilience issues to collectively address. In this regard, bridging organizations or entities have been recognised to play a crucial role, in bringing together science and local knowledge, and provide an arena for knowledge co-production, trust building, sense making, learning, vertical and horizontal collaboration, and conflict resolution (Berkes, 2009).

As we discussed above, for social learning to occur in governance regimes, however, changes should be observed not only among the stakeholders being engaged in the participatory processes enacted to foster it, but also within: (1) the organizations and economic sectors that these actors represent and/or come from; and (2) the institutional setting in which they operate. Although this has been broadly recognized in the social learning literature (Armitage et al., 2008; Medema et al., 2014; Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Reed et al., 2010), traditional evaluation of social learning outcomes mostly remains confined to measuring tools addressed to identify changes within the individuals involved in the participatory processes. This still says little about any spill-over effect that such changes can create in wider social settings, such as in the

organizations and economic sectors to which these actors belong, or the institutional setting in which they operate.

1.3.3 Strengthening the C2B2 LivingLabs approach through social learning

In general, LLs can serve effectively as bridging entities that can enable participation of multiple actors across sectors and governance levels, orchestration among multiple epistemologies and worldviews, the co-production of knowledge and the development of a common vision and social learning agendas. More specifically, as highlighted above, enabling and fostering social learning among all involved actors is one of the main functions of LLs, and one of the core objectives of the LivingLabs to be designed and set-up in the C2B2 case study areas.

To be effective, the C2B2 LLs should therefore ensure, as far as they can, that the enabling factors pertaining to the content, process, and context dimensions of social learning are in place (see above). In Table 2 below, we provide a summary of the key dimensions and enabling factors to take into account when designing and setting-up the C2B2 LivingLabs, as part of the overall C2B2 LL methodology to be implemented.

Table 2: Summary of the key LLs dimensions and social learning enabling factors.

LivingLabs key dimensions	Social Learning enabling factors
<p>The C2B2 LLs functions should:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) enable experimentation in real-life contexts and (2) facilitate recursive social learning among all actors involved. <p>Effectively facilitate experimentation and social learning among all involved stakeholders.</p>	<p>From a content perspective, all C2B2 LLs' activities, especially (a) the identification of shared problems and desired outcomes; (b) the development of a common vision; and (c) the establishment of a social learning agenda should be:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>System-oriented and grounded on system thinking;</i> 2. <i>Based on local knowledge, needs and desires;</i> 3. <i>Informed by climate and ecosystem science and insights from the ocean governance field;</i> 4. <i>Directed towards social-ecological resilience and sustainability outcomes; and</i> 5. <i>Applied to ocean governance issues in real-life context.</i>
<p>The C2B2 LLs structure should enable the development of an open innovation ecosystem that is:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) geographically embedded in real places; (2) based on the inputs gained from the participants; and (3) directed towards territorializing social innovation in specific regions (or social areas of influence) at a more manageable scale (Voytenko et al., 2016). 	<p>From an internal context perspective, C2B2 LLs should:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Ensure the technical and social competences to carry out LLs activities;</i> 2. <i>Ensure tolerance of ambiguity and diversity of opinions;</i> 3. <i>Enable flexibility and open-mindedness;</i> 4. <i>Foster awareness of resilience and sustainability issues;</i> 5. <i>Enhance the capability of all involved actors for critical self-reflection;</i> 6. <i>Ensure actors' commitment to share knowledge and learn;</i> 7. <i>Ensure reliability and consistency of all LLs activities;</i> 8. <i>Ensure respectfulness towards each other's' feelings and perspectives</i>

LivingLabs key dimensions	Social Learning enabling factors
<p>A diverse range of stakeholders from the quadruple helix (public sector, private sector, academia & civil society) should be involved in the co-creation process as early as possible.</p> <p>The C2B2 LLs therefore should enact participatory processes to facilitate knowledge co-production among all actors involved about the common problems and associated needs to be addressed, the common vision and desired outcomes to be achieved, and the kind of experiment to be conducted in order to address such problems and achieve such outcomes.</p>	<p>From a process perspective, all C2B2 LLs' activities, should</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prevent detrimental power dynamics; 2. Ensure inclusiveness, especially the inclusion of the most vulnerable people and sectors; 3. Ensure transdisciplinarity; 4. Enable knowledge co-production; 5. Ensure transparency and accountability in scenario analysis, planning activities, and achieving desired outcomes; 6. Enable mutual learning; 7. Enable the convergence of goals; 8. Build trust among all involved actors; 9. Create local value by addressing local needs and desires; 10. Ensure incorporation of the co-created knowledge into decision-making and regional planning; 11. Ensure co-ownership of LLs' activities and outcomes.

Source: The authors

As illustrated in Table 2 above, the development of a common vision and the establishment of a social learning agenda among all involved actors in the LLs are crucial **content enabling factors** for social learning to occur.

In the C2B2 LLs, a common vision consists of the commonly-agreed problems and needs to be addressed as well as desired outcomes to be achieved. The social learning agenda of the C2B2 LLs should thus reflect this vision and make it operational in terms of: (1) the specific LLs activities to be co-designed and implemented to achieve such a common vision; and (2) the specific changes at the individual, social-relational, organizational and institutional levels that are needed to let all involved actors in the LLs, co-design and implement such activities and achieve such a vision.

As discussed above, inclusive, transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes and negotiation among all actors and disciplines involved in LLs are crucial **process enabling factors** for the development of a common vision, the establishment of a social learning agenda and, therefore, for social learning to occur. However, in LLs, as well as in any other transdisciplinary context, the development of a common vision and the establishment of a social learning agenda are processes during which pre-existing power asymmetries become most evident and may be reproduced or even exacerbated. In these contexts, funding bodies, researchers and practitioners may exert instrumental and/or structural or discursive power, influencing the selection of actors, the setting of the rules and the establishment of the social learning agenda (Baxter, 2022; Fritz & Binder, 2020a; Laborgne et al., 2021; Taylor, 2021).

Too often, these processes are subject to elite control, which in the context of LLs might be the project consortium or key project partners, including specific local stakeholders (Fritz & Binder, 2020b; Laborgne et al., 2021). As discussed in the LL literature, there are three forms

of power that may be exerted and which may hinder genuine inclusiveness and mutual learning among all actors involved in LLs: first face power, second face power and third face power, which are, respectively (Laborgne et al., 2021):

“The power to put a topic on the agenda convincing the parties that it is in everyone’s interest (first face of power) (Dahl, 1957), to limit the potential topics to those which are innocuous to one party (second face of power) ((Bachrach & Baratz, 1962), omit information, creating information asymmetry, that allows for a narrative around those topics convenient to one party (third face of power) (Lukes, 2004).

To counteract such shortcomings, key lessons from LL application highlight the need for the C2B2 LLs to prevent detrimental power dynamics, by ensuring diversity, transparency and gendered analysis in the selection and recruitment of stakeholders, and by making divergent perspectives being equally considered and valued, avoiding top-down technological fixes and embracing more ‘co-creation’ as a philosophy and an approach (Beaudoin et al., 2022; Mbatha & Musango, 2022; Rizzo et al., 2021).

To achieve this, **inclusiveness** should be considered as a key principle that all LLs should respect and put into practice (Laborgne et al., 2021). This principle should meaningfully inform the participatory processes that the C2B2 LLs enact to co-produce knowledge, enable negotiation and, therefore, develop each C2B2 LLs’ common vision and establish their respective social learning agenda. Achieving the highest rate of inclusiveness as possible is crucial for the C2B2 LLs, since it helps to better understand the variety of issues, needs, and perspectives surrounding complex problems, as well as of ideas and solutions that can be developed to address such problems (Laborgne et al., 2021).

As discussed in the LLs literature (Laborgne et al., 2021), key interrelated **enabling context factors** that ensure effective inclusiveness in LLs activities relate to time, LLs’ design and implementation, trust, transparency and accountability, mutual learning, and to the need to build on local needs, create local value and enable collective ownership. **Time** factors relate to the issue that transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes surrounding the identification of common problems and desired outcomes, the development of a common vision, negotiation and the setting of a social learning agenda are all processes that demand adequate time allocation for the C2B2 LLs activities and C2B2 LLs project staff. Furthermore, early engagement of stakeholders is crucial to ensure that all actors can contribute to the identification of the common problems, associated needs and desired outcomes, and to the development of the LLs common vision.

Moreover, to ensure inclusiveness, it is crucial that **set up and implementation** of the C2B2 LLs is a joint effort made by all involved stakeholders and that they reflect a common vision co-developed by all involved actors. Such a common vision should be the result of genuine **mutual learning** among all involved stakeholders which, as discussed above, should be addressed to: (1) enhance understanding of each other’s perspectives and needs; (2) the common problems that underpin a variety of perspectives and needs and that should be addressed; (3) the likely solutions and experimentation to be designed and implemented; and (4) the lessons to be learned from the outcomes of such experimentation.

To ensure that no one's perspective and needs are left behind, **transparency** of this process is crucial as well as **accountability** of the experimentation outcomes and their evaluation in the contexts of the C2B2 LLs, against the common desired objectives. Transparency and accountability of these processes enable the development of **trust** among all involved actors which in turn enhances mutual learning, and the co-design and implementation of the C2B2 LLs' activities and related evaluation.

Finally, to be inclusive, it is crucial that common vision, activities and related evaluation of the C2B2 LLs reflect a code of conduct for participant that helps to prevent power dynamics and unbalances. The development of a common vision, activities and related evaluation should also reflect **local needs and desires**, especially of the most vulnerable actors and sectors of society, so to create tangible **local value** for everyone and concrete incentives for overcoming typical motivational barriers and thus fostering active participation. These incentives can be reinforced through: (1) commitments from local and national decision-makers to **incorporate the co-created knowledge into policy and planning practice**; (2) commitments from researchers to hand-over LLs to local communities and from local communities to take over **co-ownership of LLs activities and outcomes** (Laborgne et al., 2021).

Based on these reflections, the approach and methodology used to set up and implement the C2B2 LLs in WP4 of the C2B2 programme in order to co-create participatory and adaptive ocean governance and management in Sweden (see above), will ensure that the principle of inclusiveness are fully respected and that the enabling factors pertaining to the content, process, and context dimensions of social learning will be in place and inform the set up and implementation of these LLs (see Table 2 above).

The C2B2 LLs approach and methodology will therefore combine the strengths of LLs as recently applied to sustainable environmental governance and spatial planning with the deeper understanding of operational aspects of social learning, which we discussed above. By combining the practical advances achieved by the most recent application of LLs with the environmental governance discourse and the theoretical advances on social learning provided in this report, the aim of the overall C2B2 LL approach and methodology is to overcome the shortcomings of traditional LLs, and make LLs effective tools to enhance transformative learning and foster transformative change towards a participatory and adaptive environmental governance (i.e. ocean governance) and sustainable development (i.e. sustainable blue economy).

Chapter 2: C2B2 LL methodology for triggering transformative change via social learning in LivingLabs

In this section, we provide an overview of the overall C2B2 LL methodology, the guiding principles that will drive the C2B2 LLs design and implementation, the envisaged C2B2 LL's stages and activities, outcomes, and interaction with other C2B2 WPs, and a generic description of the implementation of the C2B2 LLs methodology in each case study.

2.1 Introduction

The C2B2 LivingLabs methodology for co-creating participatory ocean governance and adaptive management is based on validated approaches during previous implementations of LivingLabs for environmental governance challenges: e.g. Ground Truth 2.0 (Wehn & Pfeiffer, 2019; MICS (Wehn, 2021), MAR2PROTECT (Wehn, Somerwill and Bilbao Erezkano, 2023) and grounded in social-ecological systems and social learning (see *Section 1.3*). It is triggered by the need to foster a more resilient and sustainable social-ecological marine system and blue economy in Sweden. To achieve this, the core goals of the C2B2 LLs methodology and approach and all C2B2 LLs-related activities are to:

- (1) engage relevant actors across multiple sectors and governance levels operating in marine environments and interested in marine spatial planning in the C2B2 LLs;
- (2) enhance social learning among all actors involved in the C2B2 LLs, within the organizations to which they belong and at the institutional setting in which they operate; and, thus,
- (3) bring about transformative change towards a more participatory ocean governance and adaptive management across multiple governance levels and blue economy sectors in Sweden, supported by relevant and insightful data and knowledge.

The C2B2 LLs methodology for co-creating participatory ocean governance in Sweden will be applied and validated in three LLs in the three C2B2 case studies, which are located in three main marine basins of Sweden and are characterized by different social, cultural and political-institutional conditions. These LLs are *LL North*, in the Northern region of Sweden (Gulf of Bothnia); *LL East*, in the Eastern region (Baltic Sea); and *LL West*, in the Western regions (the Kattegat-Skagerrak Sea).

Overall, the C2B2 LL methodology comprises the following:

- Overarching **guiding principles** to guide the implementation of the C2B2 LLs
- Stipulations for the type of **core stakeholders** to be engaged in the LLs
- **Key stages** for setting up and implementing LLs, with a generic list of activities and envisaged outcomes per stage; based on content, process and context dimensions that enable transformative learning to occur among all involved actors and across multiple blue economy sectors and governance levels
- A **compendium** with a collection of instructions, worksheets and guidelines that accompanies the C2B2 LL teams in their 'journey' throughout each stage of setting up and implementing the C2B2 LLs. This generic Compendium will be used and completed by each C2B2 LLteam, serving also as a workspace.

- **Dedicated LL teams of C2B2 partners per case study**, who will meet regularly, and will be mentored and supported in the implementation of the activities comprised in each stage, according to the guidance provided in the compendium (see *Part 2*).

2.2 C2B2 LL definition, guiding principles & core stakeholders for the C2B2 LLs

Based on the context and aims of the C2B2 programme, the C2B2 LivingLabs are defined as (virtual or physical) arenas that put quintuple helix actors in real-life settings in Sweden (across multiple sectors and governance levels in marine environments and interested in marine spatial planning) at the centre of the social innovation process of co-creating participatory ocean governance and adaptive management.

The implementation of the C2B2 LLs will be informed by the following guiding principles:

- Create **value** for stakeholders by understanding their needs and motivations
- Enable stakeholders to **influence** decisions they are affected by
- Aim for long-term economic, social and environmental **sustainability**
- Involve multiple perspectives and collaborate widely for **openness**
- Carry out activities in a **real-life context**

In order to fully capture the potential of LivingLabs as innovation experiments and generate a comprehensive vision for participatory ocean governance in real-life and applied settings, a diverse range of stakeholders from the quintuple helix (public sector, private sector, academia & civil society) should be involved in the co-creation process as early as possible, namely:

- *industry/private sector (Offshore installations; fishing; transport)*
- *public sector actors: e.g. legislative (policy/decision-makers); executive (authorities, implementing agencies)*
- *scientists, academics*
- *citizens, communities and/or civil society organisations*
- *nature (represented by innovative data streams)*

No single stakeholder (pre)defines the challenge that each C2B2 LivingLab will address. Nevertheless, the specific roles of the stakeholders involved in the co-creation process may differ according to cultural contexts and the co-creation dynamics can be adjusted accordingly.

2.3 Stages of the C2B2 LivingLabs prototype methodology

Figure 7: Overview of the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology stages

Source: The authors

As illustrated above (see Figure 7), the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology consists of the following stages: *Prepare*, *Form*, *Explore*, *Embed*, and *Evaluate & Sustain*. Several of these stages consist of carefully designed social interaction moments with relevant stakeholders to set up the LivingLab and to co-create participatory ocean governance and adaptive management. Iterations of distinct stages and stakeholder interactions may be necessary on a case-by-case basis to ensure stage-specific objectives are met.

Table 3: Stages and activity clusters of the C2B2 LivingLabs prototype methodology

C2B2 LL methodology stages & activity clusters	Interactions with C2B2 WPs	Envisaged outputs/outcomes
<p>Stage 1: Prepare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up org. team for the C2B2 LivingLab • Rapid context analysis & problem scoping • Preliminary time plan • Extend initial stakeholder analysis • Tailor methods to context 	<p><u>Inputs from WP1</u> Synthesis of offshore ecosystems in the C2B2 case study areas Land-sea interaction in the offshore blue economy</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP3</u> Status quo of the governance processes and structures, key public sector stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Appointment of C2B2 team members for LL ▪ Social-ecological marine system pre-selected by the C2B2 team members ▪ Summary of contextual info for LL activities per case ▪ Preliminary scoping of the problems ▪ Team vision for participatory ocean governance ▪ Initial set of relevant LL stakeholders identified & invited ▪ Sound set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures
<p>Stage 2: Form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch the LivingLab • Identify & invite additional stakeholders • Agree on principles for collaboration • Develop a <i>common vision & shared goals</i> • Identify data & knowledge gaps 	<p><u>Inputs from WP1:</u> conditions of the natural resources of the social-ecological system per case</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP3:</u> status quo of (multifunctional) ocean governance processes and structures</p> <p><u>Outputs to WP2:</u> ▪ Data & knowledge gaps (requirements)</p>	<p>Principles for collaboration in the LL agreed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Initial knowledge integration across disciplines & stakeholders (merging perspectives) ▪ <i>Common vision & shared goals</i> about the problem(s) and desired outcomes ▪ Additional LL stakeholders identified & invited
<p>Stage 3: Explore</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiation and establishment of a <i>social learning agenda</i> and associated rules, roles and responsibilities • Iterative co-creation of actions & data-driven innovations • Foster <i>Horizontal interactions</i> among stakeholders at same governance level & across the C2B2 LLs • Strengthen capacity of LL stakeholders to use tools & methods for assessments & simulations, if needed 	<p><u>Inputs from WP1:</u> tools & models for assessments and simulations</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP2:</u> New data & knowledge about offshore ecosystems from open data collection platforms</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP3:</u> Scenarios for transition towards a multifunctional and sustainable blue economy, comparative policy-based tools, international marine spatial planning out-of-the-box tools</p> <p><u>Interactions across the three C2B2 LLs</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Further knowledge integration ▪ Co-creation of agreed activities and concerted actions to address the agreed problems and achieve the agreed outcomes ▪ <i>Social Learning Agenda</i> with identified transformative changes that are needed at individual, social/organizational and institutional levels to implement actions, address problems and achieve desired outcomes ▪ <i>Socio-relational</i>: improvements in the social interactions among the LL actors ▪ <i>Technological</i> data-driven innovative approaches tested and evaluated ▪ <i>Organisational</i>: raised awareness & reflection in the organisations of the LL participants

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Preliminary understanding of required changes in the governance setting (e.g. norms & organisational practices, regulatory frameworks, protocols & procedures) ▪ Strengthened capacity of LL stakeholders to use selected tools & methods for assessments & simulations.
<p>Stage 4: Embed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster <i>Horizontal interactions</i> among stakeholders at same governance level & across the C2B2 LLs • <i>Upward integrations</i> of social learning outcomes across multiple governance levels & across the C2B2 LLs • <i>Downward integrations</i>: iterative (and recursive) social learning among actors, across multiple governance levels 	<p><u>Interactions (e.g. fostering dialogue and reflection):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ across the three C2B2 LLs ▪ with sister projects & higher/national level policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lower-level social learning outcomes integrated and scaled-up across wider governance levels ▪ Strengthened horizontal interactions (capacity) and upwards integrations ▪ <i>Institutional</i>: single/double/triple loop learning ▪ Changes in norms, organisational procedures, regulatory frameworks and protocols
<p>Stage 5: Evaluate & Sustain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-evaluation of results & identify lessons learned • Decision on future of the LivingLab • Strengthen capacity of LL stakeholders: embed co-creation as routines for participatory ocean governance and a sustainable blue economy 	<p>Lessons on transitioning towards participatory ocean governance and sustainable blue economy:</p> <p><u>Outputs to T4.6:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Insights for scientific analysis <p><u>Outputs to WP3:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Insights for planning & mgt audience (recommendations & governance lessons) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthened capacity of institutional actors to embed co-creation as routines for ocean governance

Source: The authors

2.4 Implementation of the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology in the case studies

The C2B2 LL compendium (detailed in Part 2 of this report) will be a key mechanism to guide the organising team of each C2B2 LL through the implementation stages of the C2B2 LL methodology. The generic compendium will be used to set up a dedicated online compendium for each C2B2 LivingLab. It is a collection of instructions, worksheets and guidelines, as well as a safe (confidential) workspace for the C2B2 LivingLab teams. Per stage, the compendium outlines the objectives; measures of completion; and a checklist of actions with tools and guidance for the implementation.

The compendium is intended to:

- (1) guide the C2B2 team in the set up and implementation of LLs in three marine basins in the Northern (Gulf of Bothnia), Eastern (Baltic Sea) and Western (Kattegat-Skagerrak) regions of Sweden;
- (2) ensure that the principle of inclusiveness is well-understood and supported, and the enabling dynamics, dimensions, and enabling content, process and context factors of social learning are in place in each stage of LLs' implementation; and
- (3) orient LLs activities in each stage towards achieving transformative learning outcomes at the individual, social relational/organizational and institutional levels.

C2B2 LL teams are formed to set up and implement each LivingLab, one team per case (LL North, LL East, LL West), each team consisting of the respective LL lead, WP1-3 experts and IHE team members.

The process of working with the compendium is as follows:

1. T4.1 Task lead IHE Delft prepares guidance related to the C2B2 LL methodology that inform the activities in all three C2B2 case studies. These instructions are the same for all cases and these are collated in the generic compendium template. Each case study uses their own copy of the compendium as a workspace.
2. The C2B2 LivingLab teams use their respective compendium to record and report all results of their LivingLabs set-up and implementation activities, jointly filling in the document over time. This ensures all information is easily accessible for all tasks in C2B2, without the need for much coordination.
3. The progressive completion of the compendium [i.e. completion of tables in the main text and the respective compendium annexes, as requested] feeds into and is undertaken during the regular LL team teleconferences and discussions. Short tables are included in the main sections, whereas long and expanding tables are included in compendium annexes.

3. Conclusions and next steps

This report has presented the rationale and the prototype version of the tailored C2B2 LivingLabs methodology (Part 1) and the generic compendium for stages 1 and 2 of the methodology (Part 2). It combines state of the art insights on how to set up LivingLabs with effective social learning processes among key stakeholders in order to trigger change towards participatory ocean governance. For the LL teams of each C2B2 case study, the compendium included in this report (in Part 2), along with continued coaching, will be a key mechanism for guiding the sound implementation of the three C2B2 LivingLabs.

The implementation of this approach by C2B2 presents a unique opportunity to drive change in ocean governance in Sweden (see Figure 8). C2B2 will be working bottom up in each of the LivingLabs while combining their evolving insights and generated momentum via peer learning (T4.5) with the sister C2B2 LivingLabs as well as other ongoing reference projects. In addition, strategic engagement of and commitment from policy makers at higher governance levels in Sweden will inform necessary legislative and regulatory changes.

While this report has presented the initial prototype version of the C2B2 LL methodology, the final version of the methodology will be developed by the C2B2 partners during the course of the programme.

Figure 8 Driving transformative change in ocean governance in Sweden via LivingLabs and social learning
Source: The authors, based on the C2B2 programme and adapted from Imperiale and Vanclay (2021)

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PART 2

The C2B2 LivingLabs Compendium

Introduction

1.1 The C2B2 LivingLabs methodology in a nutshell

The full C2B2 LL methodology is described in the C2B2 deliverable D4.1, Part 1.

Overall, the C2B2 LL methodology comprises the following:

- Overarching **guiding principles** to guide the implementation of the C2B2 LLs
- Stipulations for the type of **core stakeholders** to be engaged in the LLs
- **Key stages** for setting up and implementing LLs, with a generic list of activities and envisaged outcomes per stage; based on content, process and context dimensions that enable transformative learning to occur among all involved actors and across multiple blue economy sectors and governance levels
- A **compendium** with a collection of instructions, worksheets and guidelines that accompanies the C2B2 LL teams in their ‘journey’ throughout each stage of setting up and implementing the C2B2 LLs. This generic Compendium will be used and completed by each C2B2 LLteam, serving also as a workspace.
- **Dedicated LL teams of C2B2 partners per case study**, their regular interactions and structured meetings, with mentoring and coaching activities on how to implement the activities of each stage, using the guidance in the compendium.

As illustrated in Part 1, Chapter 2, the C2B2 LLs implementation Stages are 5, namely: *Prepare, Form, Explore, Embed, and Evaluate & Sustain*. All of these 5 Stages will interact with other C2B2 WPs, and are directed to achieving specific outcomes towards enabling transformative learning and fostering transformative change for more participatory ocean governance and a sustainable blue economy in Sweden. Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of all the C2B2 LL methodology stages, how they interact with the other C2B2 WPs and their envisaged outcomes.

Table 1: Stages and activity clusters of the C2B2 LivingLabs prototype methodology

C2B2 LL methodology stages & activity clusters	Interactions with C2B2 WPs	Envisaged outputs/outcomes
<p>Stage 1: Prepare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up org. team for the C2B2 LivingLab • Rapid context analysis & problem scoping • Preliminary time plan • Extend initial stakeholder analysis • Tailor methods to context 	<p><u>Inputs from WP1</u> Synthesis of offshore ecosystems in the C2B2 case study areas Land-sea interaction in the offshore blue economy</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP3</u> Status quo of the governance processes and structures, key public sector stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Appointment of C2B2 team members for LL ▪ Social-ecological marine system pre-selected by the C2B2 team members ▪ Summary of contextual info for LL activities per case ▪ Preliminary scoping of the problems ▪ Team vision for participatory ocean governance ▪ Initial set of relevant LL stakeholders identified & invited ▪ Sound set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures
<p>Stage 2: Form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch the LivingLab • Identify & invite additional stakeholders • Agree on principles for collaboration • Develop a <i>common vision & shared goals</i> • Identify data & knowledge gaps 	<p><u>Inputs from WP1:</u> conditions of the natural resources of the social-ecological system per case</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP3:</u> status quo of (multifunctional) ocean governance processes and structures</p> <p><u>Outputs to WP2:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data & knowledge gaps (requirements) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Principles for collaboration in the LL agreed ▪ Initial knowledge integration across disciplines & stakeholders (merging perspectives) ▪ <i>Common vision & shared goals</i> about the problem(s) and desired outcomes ▪ Additional LL stakeholders identified & invited
<p>Stage 3: Explore</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiation and establishment of a <i>social learning agenda</i> and associated rules, roles and responsibilities • Iterative co-creation of actions & data-driven innovations • Foster <i>Horizontal interactions</i> among stakeholders at same governance level & across the C2B2 LLs • Strengthen capacity of LL stakeholders to use tools & methods for assessments & simulations, if needed 	<p><u>Inputs from WP1:</u> tools & models for assessments and simulations</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP2:</u> New data & knowledge about offshore ecosystems from open data collection platforms</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP3:</u> Scenarios for transition towards a multifunctional and sustainable blue economy, comparative policy-based tools, international marine spatial planning out-of-the-box tools</p> <p><u>Interactions across the three C2B2 LLs</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Further knowledge integration ▪ Co-creation of agreed activities and concerted actions to address the agreed problems and achieve the agreed outcomes ▪ <i>Social Learning Agenda</i> with identified transformative changes that are needed at individual, social/organizational and institutional levels to implement actions, address problems and achieve desired outcomes ▪ <i>Socio-relational</i>: improvements in the social interactions among the LL actors ▪ <i>Technological</i> data-driven innovative approaches tested and evaluated ▪ <i>Organisational</i>: raised awareness & reflection in the organisations of the LL participants ▪ Preliminary understanding of required changes in the governance setting (e.g. norms & organisational

		<p>practices, regulatory frameworks, protocols & procedures)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthened capacity of LL stakeholders to use selected tools & methods for assessments & simulations.
<p>Stage 4: Embed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster <i>Horizontal interactions</i> among stakeholders at same governance level & across the C2B2 LLs • <i>Upward integrations</i> of social learning outcomes across multiple governance levels & across the C2B2 LLs • <i>Downward integrations</i>: iterative (and recursive) social learning among actors, across multiple governance levels 	<p><u>Interactions (e.g. fostering dialogue and reflection):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ across the three C2B2 LLs ▪ with sister projects & higher/national level policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lower-level social learning outcomes integrated and scaled-up across wider governance levels ▪ Strengthened horizontal interactions (capacity) and upwards integrations ▪ <i>Institutional</i>: single/double/triple loop learning ▪ Changes in norms, organisational procedures, regulatory frameworks and protocols
<p>Stage 5: Evaluate & Sustain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-evaluation of results & identify lessons learned • Decision on future of the LivingLab • Strengthen capacity of LL stakeholders: embed co-creation as routines for participatory ocean governance and a sustainable blue economy 	<p>Lessons on transitioning towards participatory ocean governance and sustainable blue economy:</p> <p><u>Outputs to T4.6:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Insights for scientific analysis <p><u>Outputs to WP3:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Insights for planning & mgt audience (recommendations & governance lessons) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthened capacity of institutional actors to embed co-creation as routines for ocean governance

1.2 Working with the C2B2 LivingLabs Compendium

The compendium is a collection of instructions, worksheets and guidelines that accompanies the C2B2 LL teams in their ‘journey’ throughout each stage of setting up and implementing the C2B2 LLs. This generic Compendium will be used and completed by each C2B2 LLteam, serving also as a workspace.

The compendium is structured according to the stages of the C2B2 LL methodology (see Figure below). Each stage consists of a number of activities that need to be completed before advancing to the next stage. Iterations of activities may be necessary to ensure that stage-specific objectives are met. Next to the description of the detailed activities per stage, the guidance provided in this compendium includes the overarching objectives of each stage together with measure(s) of whether the objectives have been reached.

C2B2 LL teams are formed to set up and implement each LivingLab, one team per case (LL North, LL East, LL West), each team consisting of the respective LL lead, and thematic experts from WP1-4. The process of working with the compendium is as follows:

1. T4.1 Task lead IHE Delft prepares guidance related to the C2B2 LL methodology that inform the activities in all three C2B2 case studies. These instructions are the same for all cases and these are collated in the generic compendium template. Each case study uses their own copy of the compendium as a workspace.
2. The C2B2 LivingLab teams use their respective compendium to record and report all results of their LivingLabs set-up and implementation activities, jointly filling in the document over time. This ensures all information is easily accessible for all tasks in C2B2, without the need for much coordination.

3. The progressive completion of the compendium [i.e. completion of tables in the main text and the respective compendium annexes, as requested] feeds into and is undertaken during the regular LL team teleconferences and discussions. Short tables are included in the main sections, whereas long and expanding tables are included in compendium annexes.

The overarching task for the **C2B2 Case Study Leaders** in this LivingLabs process is to manage, on the one hand, the team of C2B2 case study partners and, on the other, to make sure that all contributing stakeholders are kept informed and engaged during the LivingLab lifetime.

1.3 Guiding principles & core stakeholders of C2B2 LivingLabs

The guiding principles for the C2B2 LivingLabs (Ståhlbröst & Holst, 2017) are as follows:

- Create **value** for stakeholders by understanding their needs and motivations
- Enable stakeholders to **influence** decisions they are affected by
- Aim for long-term economic, social and environmental **sustainability**
- Involve multiple perspectives and collaborate widely for **openness**
- Carry out activities in a **real-life context**

In order to fully capture the potential of LivingLabs as innovation experiments and generate a comprehensive vision for participatory ocean governance in real-life and applied settings, a diverse range of stakeholders from the quintuple (public sector, private sector, academia, civil society and nature) should be involved in the co-creation process as early as possible, namely:

- private sector (Offshore installations; fishing; transport)
- public sector actors (from different governance levels)
- academia (researcher, scientists from different disciplines)
- civil society organisations, communities and/or citizens
- nature (represented by innovative data streams)

No single stakeholder (pre)defines the problem that each LivingLab will address. Nevertheless, the specific roles of the stakeholders involved in the co-creation process may differ according to cultural contexts and the co-creation dynamics can be adjusted accordingly.

Stage 1: Prepare

Introduction

As briefly sketched in Part 1 of D4.1 (see Part 1, Section 3.3), the **Prepare** stage serves to establish a C2B2 LL team in each case study (consisting of the respective LL lead, and WP1-4 thematic experts). The C2B2 LL team defines **the specific social-ecological marine system** on which each LL will focus, and conducts an **initial context analysis** related to the social-ecological marine system under consideration. The context analysis will be fed by the insights from climate and ecosystem science which will be provided to the C2B2 LL team by C2B2 WP1, and by the insights from the ocean governance and adaptive management field which will be provided by C2B2 WP3.

The context analysis informed by these insights will then lead to a preliminary scoping of the main issues that influence the achievement of a resilient and sustainable social-ecological marine system and a sustainable blue economy in the respective region of each C2B2 LL. The identification of the social-ecological system and context analysis and the **preliminary scoping of the main problems** will then serve as the basis for the C2B2 LL team to discuss and establish the **team vision** about the desired participatory ocean governance that is intended to be achieved and the transformative changes needed to achieve it in their case study.

Next, the identification of the specific social-ecological marine system to be considered, the context analysis, the preliminary scoping of the problems, and the establishment of the team vision will feed the **identification of the initial set of relevant C2B2 LL stakeholders**, and a **sound set up of stakeholder management tools and procedures**. Below, we provide an overview of the cluster of activities to be conducted in this stage, the envisaged outputs/outcomes to be achieved and the interactions that C2B2 LL teams will have with other C2B2 WPs. The overview below also includes a list of the **main objectives** to be achieved by the C2B2 LL teams in this stage, a **checklist of the activities** to be carried out and **measures of completion**.

Stages & activity clusters	Interactions with C2B2 WPs	Envisaged outputs/outcomes
<p>Prepare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Set up org. team for the C2B2 LivingLab ▪ Rapid context analysis & problem scoping ▪ Preliminary time plan ▪ Extend initial stakeholder analysis ▪ Tailor methods to context 	<p><u>Inputs from WP1:</u> Land-sea interaction in the offshore blue economy</p> <p><u>Inputs from WP3:</u> Status quo of the governance processes and structures, key public sector stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Appointment of C2B2 team members for the LivingLab ▪ Social-ecological marine system pre-selected by the C2B2 team members ▪ Summary of contextual info for LL activities per case ▪ Preliminary scoping of the problems ▪ Team vision for participatory ocean governance ▪ Initial set of relevant LL stakeholders identified & invited

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sound set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures
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Main objectives

- **Appointment of team members** for the C2B2 LivingLab;
- Identify the specific **social-ecological marine system** to be consider;
- **Analyse the context** of the C2B2 LivingLab activities in the case study area;
- **Preliminary scoping of the problems** agreed by the C2B2 team members;
- **Develop a team vision** concerning participatory ocean governance and the transformative change needed to achieve it in the specific region agreed by the C2B2 team members
- **Stakeholders analysis** for the formation of the C2B2 LivingLab;
- Sound set up of **stakeholder management tools and procedures**.

Measure(s) of completion

- Identification of the specific marine social-ecological system and context analysis completed;
- Preliminary problem scoping completed
- Team vision established
- List of 15-25 stakeholders identified and invited to participate in the C2B2 LivingLab;
- Stakeholder management tool completed with initial stakeholder details;
- Indication of compliance with procedures for stakeholder data processing.

Stage 1 Actions	Status
ACTION 1.1: Indicate the appointment of team members for your C2B2 LivingLab in Table 1.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 1.2: Identify the specific social-ecological marine system to be considered and complete the context analysis table in Annex 1	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 1.3: Discuss and agree on the preliminary scoping of the main problems. Please capture the result of your discussion in Annex 2.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 1.4: Discuss and agree on the LL team's vision of participatory ocean governance for the case study and capture it Table 2.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 1.5: Discuss and agree on the tentative timing of per stage of the C2B2 LL methodology for your case study and capture the result of your discussion in Annex 3.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 1.6: Identify the stakeholders to be involved in the LL of your case study, using the mindmap in an online tool of your choice (Miro, shared PPT, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 1.7: For each stakeholder identified in Action 1.6, include detailed contact information in the Stakeholder Management table in Annex 4.	<input type="checkbox"/>

In the subsections below, we provide a description of these actions (*Actions 1.1-1.7*) and more detailed instructions on how to complete them and the tools to be used for this purpose.

1.1 Appointment of C2B2 LL team members

Setting up the LivingLab activities is a team effort of several C2B2 partner organisations and their staff members. In order for the LL team in this case stud to work well together, there needs to be clarity about the appointment of specific C2B2 staff members to distinct roles in the C2B2 LivingLab, who to invite to the regular site teleconferences and other issues.

Action 1.1

Indicate the appointment of C2B2 team members for the LL in your case study in Table 1.

If there is staff turnover during the lifetime of the C2B2 programme life time, please update this table accordingly.

Table 1: C2B2 team members for the LL in this case study

Role	C2B2 team member	Back up contact
Case study lead		
WP1 Climate & ecosystem science		
WP2 Data-driven innovation		
WP3 Governance expertise		
WP4 Guidance on LivingLabs (IHE)		

1.2 Social-ecological marine system identification and context analysis

It is important to capture and understand the context in which the C2B2 LivingLab activities are to be embedded. In C2B2, this relates primarily to the respective social-ecological marine system in which the three C2B2 LLs will be established. As we discussed in Part 1 of C2B2 deliverable D4.1, a key content factor that enables social learning to occur among all actors involved in a LL is that the framing and scoping of the problems and the identification of the desired outcomes should be system-oriented and enable system thinking capable of understanding coupled social-ecological interactions.

The identification of the social-ecological marine system will reflect the specific area of intervention where C2B2 LLs activities will be situated and on which all C2B2 LLs-related efforts will focus. This identification will be accompanied by a careful analysis of the main features that characterize the specific social-ecological marine system under consideration (McGinnis and Ostrom, 2014; Ostrom, 2015), namely:

- the social, economic, and political settings;
- the resource system; the resource units;

- the main stakeholders; and
- the main governance structures (i.e. regulatory institutions, norms and regulatory frameworks), strategies (i.e. institutional, financial, risk management, physical planning and participation strategies set up by policies) and processes (i.e. planning arrangements) that regulate social-ecological interactions in the social-ecological marine system under consideration.

Action 1.2

Identify the specific social-ecological marine system to be considered by completing the context analysis table in Annex 1.

1.3 Preliminary scoping of the main problems

The C2B2 LivingLabs will undertake activities in their respective case study areas, linked to the issues of each site. Each site has its peculiarities, as is to be detailed in the context analysis (section 1.2). While the C2B2 LivingLab provides the means to obtain substantive inputs from a wide range of relevant stakeholders, it is important that, in the preparation phase, the C2B2 partners involved in this case study have a preliminary joint understanding and agreement on the main problems that affect the resilience and sustainability of the social-ecological marine system under consideration. The preliminary scoping of the main problems should be grounded in the activities above and on the preliminary inputs received from the natural and climate science (C2B2 WP1), and from the ocean governance field (C2B2 WP3).

This preliminary scoping of the main problems will serve as a common basis upon which all members of the C2B2 LL team should agree in broader terms. This will guide the initial discussions that the team will start within its LL and will be modified, integrated, and enriched following inclusion of stakeholders' insights and perspectives.

Based on (i) the social-ecological marine system identification and context analysis (section 1.2) and (ii) on the inputs from WP1 (natural and climate science) and WP3 (ocean governance and management), please discuss with the local C2B2 LL team members the main problems that characterize the specific social-ecological marine system under consideration.

Action 1.3

Discuss and agree on the preliminary scoping of the main problems. Please capture the result of your discussion in Annex 2.

1.4 Team vision on participatory ocean governance for the case study

While most of the C2B2 LL activities will be directed towards developing a common vision and a social learning agenda with all involved actors in the LL, in the preparation phase, it is important that the C2B2 LL team members agree upon a preliminary team vision that will guide the activities addressed to foster conversation among the involved actors in the

following stages of the C2B2 LL implementation. This team vision will be about the desired participatory and adaptive ocean governance.

Key inputs are (a) the identification of the specific social-ecological marine system and context analysis (Action 1.2), (b) the inputs from WP1 and WP3, and (c) the preliminary scoping of the main problems (Action 1.3).

The stated LL team vision should be reviewed regularly during the C2B2 LivingLab team teleconferences.

Action 1.4

Discuss the LL team’s vision of participatory ocean governance for your case study and capture it in Table 2.

Table 2: Team Vision of participatory ocean governance for this case study agreed by the C2B2 LL team

LL Team vision of participatory ocean governance for this case study (short version)	Explanation of agreed C2B2 LivingLab team vision about the desired participatory ocean governance and adaptive management in your case study.

1.5 Tentative timing

As part of scoping the team vision of your C2B2 LivingLab, it is important to define the tentative timing. This will provide continuous means for monitoring and evaluation of progress with the set up and implementation of the LivingLab in your case study, in terms of progress through the C2B2 LL methodology stages.

Action 1.5

Discuss and agree on the tentative timing per stage of the C2B2 LL methodology in your case study and capture the result of your discussion in Annex 3.

1.6 Stakeholder analysis for the LivingLab

The specific common vision and social learning agenda for which the LivingLab in this C2B2 case study will co-design participatory ocean governance will be identified and agreed upon with all stakeholders once the LL has been launched. This is different from the vision agreed upon in the section above, which represents only the perspective of the C2B2 LL team.

The methodology stipulates that **no single stakeholder fully (pre)defines the specific common vision and social learning agenda that the LivingLab activities will address** (see guiding principles in the introduction).

A diverse range of stakeholders needs to be involved in the LivingLab in order to fully unleash its potential to drive transformative change towards participatory ocean governance. In the C2B2 context of off-shore activities, these are as follows:

- *private sector (Offshore installations; fishing; transport)*
- *public sector actors (from different governance levels)*
- *academia (researcher, scientists from different disciplines)*
- *civil society organisations, communities and/or citizens*
- *nature (represented by innovative data streams)*

The LivingLab will consist of selected persons (typically around 15-25 people) representing the stakeholder groups listed above (and illustrated in the sunburst below), who are willing to participate in the LivingLab activities and to co-design participatory ocean governance in the case study in order to address specific socio-ecological issues.

In order to identify relevant stakeholders for each category from the quintuple helix, a tailored stakeholder analysis is required. This is the process of **identifying** the individuals, groups of people and/or organizations that are likely to **impact or be impacted** by **the C2B2 LivingLab activities** (and its focus on co-creating transformative change towards participatory ocean governance in the specific case study context), with the intention of managing them according to their interests and concerns.

At this stage of the C2B2 LL methodology, we are primarily concerned with identifying stakeholders that will participate in the LivingLab itself. In the subsequent FORM stage of the methodology, once the core common vision and social learning agenda to be addressed by the LivingLab activities have been agreed upon, a follow up stakeholder analysis will be undertaken (also jointly with the initial LivingLab participants) in order to identify which *additional* stakeholders need to be involved or consulted. For example, depending on the selected common vision and social learning agenda, additional scientists may need to be included who are experts in relevant fields; and relevant existing civil society groups may be identified. Moreover, the stakeholders in the *external* context of the LL (shaded grey in the sunburst) will be identified.

In order to undertake this first stakeholder analysis, the structured mindmap (see image) will help to identify relevant stakeholders per quintuple helix category. You can paste it in a Miro board, shared Powerpoint or any other online tool you prefer to allow collaboration among the LL team members.

Action 1.6

Please complete use the mindmap to identify stakeholders to be involved in the LL of your case study.

While some stakeholder categories have a natural limit in terms of the maximum number of persons one can identify, others - such as citizens - provide the opportunity to diversify and to substantiate the group, especially in view of potential drop out during the LivingLab implementation. Having some people drop out of the process is not a bad thing per se; it merely reflects different levels of interests, availability and involvement.

1.7 Stakeholder data management

Over the course of the next few months, you will identify, contact and interact with a wide range of stakeholders for the LivingLab at your case study. This includes those stakeholders that will be invited to participate in the LivingLab as well as those in the external context of the LivingLab. To keep track of the preparations and interactions, and to communicate the activities within the C2B2 project for planning and research purposes, it is essential to collect stakeholder information in a structured way, using the tool provided in Action 1.7:

- Stakeholder classification acc. to quintuple helix
- Names and contact details
- Contact 'owner' from the C2B2 LL team
- Stakeholder's interest in offshore issue in the case study
- What may enable/hinder their participation in the LL
- Notes and remarks

Action 1.7

For each stakeholder identified in Action 1.6, include detailed contact information in the Stakeholder Management tool in Annex 4.

Note: The collection of personal data is subject to ethics requirements, the data management has to comply with [the procedures and principles outlined in the C2B2 Programme Handbook](#).

Stage 2: Form

Introduction

As briefly sketched in Part 1 of D4.1, in Stage 2 of the C2B2 LL methodology (**Form**), the multiple stakeholders who were identified in Stage 1 (*Prepare*) will be invited to participate in the launch workshop of the C2B2 LL in your case study. In this first LL workshop, the invited stakeholders are encouraged to agree with the principles for collaboration in the LL. The launch workshop will be carefully crafted to ensure **initial knowledge integration** among the multiple epistemologies and worldviews of the participating stakeholders.

This knowledge integration will consist of **multiple knowledge sharing activities**, including: (1) the C2B2 LL team sharing their analysis of the specific social-ecological marine system under consideration, the preliminary scoping of the problems and the team vision they developed in Stage 1; (2) the invited stakeholders sharing their analysis of the context, their perspectives on the main problems and the vision they have about the desired participatory ocean governance and the transformative changes needed to achieve it in the specific case study area. Ideally, during the Form stage, the LL will convene multiple times providing all stakeholders to reflect and further elaborate on these issues. These multiple workshops will ultimately result in everyone converging towards a **common vision** and a shared social learning agenda.

Several workshops may need to be held in order to develop a common vision, and negotiate and establish a social learning agenda. The launch workshop, beyond introducing the C2B2 program's purposes and activities, should be focused on sharing with (and gaining feedback from the participants about) the main characteristics of the social-ecological marine system identified and analyzed and the main problems pre-scoped by the C2B2 team (see Action 1.2 and 1.3). The second workshop should be focused on the current state of ocean governance, challenges related to this and the establishment of a common vision of participatory ocean governance among all LL participants. Finally, the third workshop should be focused on negotiating the social learning agenda, thus leading to the identification of the transformative changes that are needed at the individual, social/organizational and institutional levels needed to achieve the common vision.

Stages & activity clusters	Interactions with C2B2 WPs	Envisaged outputs/outcomes
Stage 2: Form <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Launch the LivingLab ▪ Identify & invite additional stakeholders ▪ Agree on principles for collaboration ▪ Develop a common vision & shared goals ▪ Identify data & knowledge gaps 	<u>Inputs from WP1:</u> conditions of the natural resources of the social-ecological system per case <u>Inputs from WP3:</u> status quo of (multifunctional) ocean governance processes and structures <u>Outputs to WP2:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data & knowledge gaps (requirements) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Principles for collaboration in the LL agreed ▪ Raised awareness of the enabling content, process and context factors of social learning for transformative change towards a sustainable blue economy. ▪ Initial knowledge integration across disciplines & stakeholders (merging perspectives) ▪ <i>Common vision & shared goals</i> about the problem(s), desired outcomes, and concerted actions to address these problems and achieve these outcomes ▪ <i>Social Learning Agenda</i> with the transformative changes needed at individual, social/organizational and institutional levels to implement actions,

		address problems and achieve the desired outcomes ■ Additional LL stakeholders identified & invited.
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Main objective of Stage 2 Form

- Targeted C2B2 LivingLabs participants invited
- Enabling environment authorities informed about the planned C2B2 LivingLab
- Understanding of cultural and local specificities for the LivingLab workshop
- Launch of the LivingLab
- Initial knowledge integration
- Problem scoping & development of a common vision of participatory ocean governance in the case study area
- Establishment of a social learning agenda

Measure(s) of completion of Stage 2 Form

- Customized invitation message for each prospective LivingLab member sent
- Completion of enabling environment briefing status
- Completion of conditions for LivingLab workshops
- LivingLab launched
- Common principles for collaboration developed and agreed upon
- Common vision developed and agreed
- Social learning agenda developed and agreed.

Stage 2 Form: List of Actions	Status
Action 2.1 Complete Table 4 with generic invitations for each stakeholder type in your case study, tailoring this as necessary for those that are already Associated Partners of the C2B2 programme	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 2.2: Contact each stakeholder, using the tailored invitations from Table 4 and an agenda invitation to the LL launch meeting. Then include information about these engagement activities in the Stakeholder Management tool (Annex 4).	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 2.3: Identify relevant stakeholders in the External context of this C2B2 LivingLab and describe them in Table 5.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 2.4: Contact each identified relevant stakeholder in the External LL context, tailoring your message to their responsibilities, then record your outreach activities in the Stakeholder Management tool (Annex 4).	
ACTION 2.5: Complete Table 6 to capture the specific conditions for the C2B2 launch workshop and other C2B2 LL's sessions in your case study	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 2.6: Adapt the generic session design for a LL launch workshop (Annex 5) to your setting	

ACTION 2.7: Immediately following the completion of the LivingLab workshop(s), hold a debriefing session of the C2B2 LL team and fill in the Logbook for this event.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 2.8: Hand out or send the evaluation form to the participants (e.g. via SurveyMonkey), ideally at the event or within 1-3 days after the workshop, then capture and analyse the results.	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACTION 2.9: Based on the discussions in the LL workshops, formulate the LivingLab's Common Vision in Annex 7, and then share it with the LL participants.	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.1 Invitation to the LivingLab workshops

In this stage, the different key stakeholders identified for the C2B2 LivingLab workshops (see Stage 1) need to be invited. This is typically done by reaching out to them via personal connections and communication (phone, email) and/or in bilateral meetings.

Stakeholders related to offshore activities are not equally powerful (e.g. due to their formal mandate) and different stakeholders are entitled to different considerations (e.g. due to their seniority, whether they are already Associated Partners of the C2B2 programme). In order to ensure their commitment to this LivingLab, it is important to relay their relevance for the process. This should be done via carefully tailored invitation messages for the above-mentioned communications.

These messages should address the following aspects:

- Why we are planning to set up a LivingLab related to the case study's offshore activities
- Why the input of stakeholder X is useful
- What stakeholder X gets out of it
- How stakeholder X can be involved

Here is an example from the MAR2PROTECT project (case study location anonymised)

Dear ...,

I hope this letter finds you well. I am writing to formally extend an invitation to you and your esteemed organization to participate as a valued stakeholder in our upcoming Living Lab for the XXX project. The MAR2PROTECT project offers a comprehensive strategy aimed at safeguarding groundwater against contamination resulting from the influences of climate change and global shifts. This strategy involves the integration of cutting-edge and complementary technologies, complemented by robust stakeholder engagement efforts, within 7 meticulously selected demonstration sites. These sites were chosen to encompass diverse climatic, political, and social contexts, as well as a range of water sources for managed aquifer recharge (MAR).

In addition to this, MAR2PROTECT establishes and executes a series of locally customized engagement strategies for MAR, collaboratively designed with stakeholders in our dedicated LivingLabs. <case study name> stands as an ideal location for a Living Lab due to its abundant water resources, diverse aquifer types, and the climate context, offering a range of conditions for research on

groundwater management and aquifer recharge. The region's geological diversity, proximity to urban areas, and access to local expertise make it a prime setting for comprehensive water-related studies. <case study name>'s ecosystem diversity, cultural attractions, and government support further enhance its suitability for hosting Living Lab activities.

A Living Lab is a collaborative approach that places users and various stakeholders, including authorities, industry professionals, researchers, and civil society, at the heart of the innovation process. In MAR2PROTECT, we set up LivingLabs to engage stakeholders in collaborative research and innovation centred around managed aquifer recharge within real-world contexts. This is where your participation will be invaluable. In the <case study name> Living Lab, we aspire to engage key stakeholders, like yourself, who play a key role in the sustainability of groundwater resources in **XX (stakeholder location)**.

Over the course of the next three years, the MAR2PROTECT Frielas Living Lab will host a series of workshops. These workshops are crucial for ensuring that the innovations introduced by the MAR2PROTECT are not only innovative but also practical and embedded in local circumstances.

Our overarching objective of MAR2PROTECT is to assess the impact of climate change and global environmental shifts on both the quality and quantity of groundwater recharge, particularly through the future injection of treated wastewater from industrial activities. In doing so, we aim to develop innovative technologies for the <case study name> demo site **(more information provided below)** and equip stakeholders with novel tools to estimate essential groundwater parameters, such as water levels and contaminant concentrations in the aquifer. Moreover, we are committed to fostering greater engagement of civil society in the realm of groundwater management and protection in <case study name>.

In this context, the involvement of **XXXXXXXXXX (institution)** in the Living Lab will provide invaluable insights that will underpin the development of MAR2PROTECT tools, assist in the identification of critical parameters for monitoring, and facilitate the co-design of various forms of societal engagement in groundwater management.

Participating in the Living Lab promises engaging interactions and discussions related to groundwater management in <case study name>. By joining, you will have the opportunity to contribute to the development of advanced, innovative tools to support aquifer monitoring and water management, with a specific focus on the <name> demo site, and forge deeper connections with a diverse range of stakeholders actively involved in the field of groundwater management.

To kickstart the Living Lab in <case study location>, we are organizing a LivingLab launch workshop. During this session, we aim to collaboratively define our shared objectives for the MAR2PROTECT <case study name> Living Lab and establish a strategic approach. The workshop is scheduled for **XX** date at **YY** hour and will take place at **LOCATION**.

We eagerly anticipate your response by **XX** date, confirming your participation or that of a suitable colleague from your organization in this inaugural workshop. Your expertise and support are integral to the success of MAR2PROTECT <case study name> Living Lab, and we look forward to the possibility of collaborating with you. Should you have any questions or require additional information, please feel free to contact me directly **at [Your Email Address] or [Your Phone Number]**.

Thank you for considering our invitation, and we anticipate a positive response.
Sincerely,

For comprehensive details about the XXX project, please visit our project website at ..

Action 2.1

Complete Table 4 with generic invitations for each stakeholder type in your case study, tailoring this as necessary for those that are already Associated Partners of the C2B2 programme.

Note: all recruitment activities have to comply with the C2B2 ethics procedures and principles outlined in the C2B2 Programme Handbook (i.e. the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants, and the protection of personal data).

Table 4: Tailored invitations for the prospective participants of the C2B2 LL in this case study

Stakeholder type	Tailored invitation message
Industry/Private sector	
Public sector actors – (per governance level/entity)	
Citizens, civil society organisations	
Academia, scientists	
Other (case-specific)	

2.2 Reach out the main stakeholders

Once drafted the email invitation for each category of stakeholders in the quintuple helix, these should be reached out preferably via email, using these tailored messages.

Action 2.2

Contact each stakeholder, using the tailored invitations from Table 4 and an agenda invitation to the LL launch meeting. Then include information about these engagement activities in the Stakeholder Management tool (Annex 4).

2.3 Reach out to enabling environment organizations

The enabling environment for offshore activities consists of a wider range of authorities such as legislators and policy makers, other than those identified for participation in the LL itself (see section 1.6, sunburst and mindmap). Not all of these can of course be involved directly; nevertheless, it is important to inform relevant contacts among these stakeholders early on

(and over time) of the C2B2 LL planned activities, so that they are aware and ideally supportive.

Moreover, this group can consist of regulatory agencies relevant for the problem under investigation, entities relevant to solutions for the problem, and supporting organisations. For example, air quality is typically considered in the remit of a city administration, but solutions may have to involve regional road authorities and additional city units, whereas support can come from provincial government in the form of valuable insights and resources.

Action 2.3

Identify relevant stakeholders in the External context of this C2B2 LivingLab and describe them in Table 5.

Table 5: Relevant stakeholders in the External context of C2B2 LLs to keep informed

External context of C2B2 LLs (organisation)	Role / Reason to inform them about planned C2B2 LivingLab in this case study area
Regulatory entities	
Interest groups	
Funders	
Media	

Important: Since the C2B2 programme is being implemented in Sweden in three parallel case studies, each with a LivingLab, it is crucial to cross-check and align with the other LL teams for common stakeholders and approach them together (e.g. joint letter to keep them informed about the C2B2 LL activities).

Action 2.4

Contact each identified relevant stakeholder in the External LL context, tailoring your message to their responsibilities, then record your outreach activities in the Stakeholder Management tool (Annex 4).

2.4 Tailoring the LivingLab activities

The LivingLab has to be tailored to this case study in terms of its local cultural setting, the history of stakeholder interactions, earlier experiences (good or bad) of collaborative work etc. The facilitation of the interactions within the workshops must be appropriate and fit the

context in which it takes place. This section therefore serves to identify the conditions for holding successful workshop-style/interactive meetings with the LivingLab participants in your C2B2 case study.

Action 2.5

Complete Table 6 to capture the specific conditions for the C2B2 launch workshop and other C2B2 LL's sessions in your case study.

Based also on this and with the support of the IHE team, please tailor the agenda for the C2B2 launch workshop in Annex 5.

Table 6: Conditions for holding workshops/interactive meetings with the LivingLab participants in the case study

Key aspects	Case study conditions
Cultural specificities (e.g. extent to which LivingLab principles can be applied here)	
Ways of interacting in meeting setting (e.g. specific customs to adhere to; language to use (e.g. Swedish only?))	
Opportunities for bringing these stakeholders together in the LivingLab	
Challenges for bringing these stakeholders together in the LivingLab	

2.5 Prepare the LL workshops (launch workshop & subsequent workshops)

Depending on the LL participants' preferences and availability, multiple workshops will be needed to achieve convergence of perspectives and goals, develop and agree upon the C2B2 LL common vision and the C2B2 social learning agenda. At least three C2B2 LL workshops should be held in order to achieve full consensus around and develop a common vision and a shared social learning agenda (see detailed explanation above). The structure of these C2B2 LL workshops is provided in Annex 5. This general design can be tailored by the C2B2 LivingLab team in the dedicated LL team telcos.

The workshops with LL participants may be held face-to-face or online, depending on the preferences and availability of the invited stakeholders per case study. It is usually advisable to hold at least the LL launch meeting F2F, subsequent meetings could be held online, if

preferred by the LL participants. Additional detailed guidance on the facilitation of the LL launch workshop and subsequent workshops will be made available during a dedicated peer learning workshop by IHE.

Action 2.6

Adapt the generic session design for a LivingLab launch workshop (Annex 5) to your setting.

The preparation and implementation of each LL workshops require the completion of the following activities.

Weeks before

1. Set the date & location and formally invite the stakeholders identified and approached bilaterally in stage 2
2. Clarify main facilitator/support roles among the C2B2 partners present to implement the workshop
3. Finalise the session design jointly in the LivingLab team telcos
4. Finalise the accompanying PPT slide set for the workshop (provided by IHE, available [here](#)) and adjust it to the specific workshop setting (e.g. facilitator name, location, date, host workshop); please adjust the activity instructions to be in line with the tailored workshop setting and the session design.

Days before

1. Prepare print outs of/send digital versions of the C2B2 informed consent sheet (see C2B2 Programme Handbook), tailored to the workshop setting (date and data manager)
2. Have post its, markers and other supporting material ready; if the workshop is held online: have the MIRO board prepared or similar prepared for collaborative process.
3. Pack the C2B2 banner and set it up in the room before the workshop starts; online: get participating partners to install C2B2 virtual backgrounds
4. Set up the room/breakout rooms with for groups of 3-4 people (max) per table

On the day of the workshop

1. Hand out the informed consent forms, then collect them at the start of the workshop
2. Take detailed minutes of the discussions
3. Take photos of the workshop

After the Workshop

1. Take photos/screen shots of all materials produced during the workshop (post its, compass posters, etc.) and file them
2. Gather all physical workshop material post its, compass posters, etc. and keep it safe
3. Hold a de-briefing (online) session (ideally on the same day) with the C2B2 team to complete the Logbook for this workshop (see Annex 9).
4. Ask participants to complete the evaluation form (template in Annex 6).

Digitise all workshop materials (write up post its, etc.) and include them in the relevant sections of this compendium.

2.6 Evaluation of the LivingLab workshops

Each LivingLab workshop needs to be evaluated in two ways:

- By the C2B2 LL team facilitating the event by means of a **de-briefing session**, jointly completing the Logbook for this event (using the format provided in Annex 6).
- By the participants by means of an evaluation form (see Annex 7), e.g. printed and handed out during the event OR sent afterwards, e.g. using SurveyMonkey).

Action 2.7

Immediately following the completion of the LivingLab workshop(s), hold a debriefing session of the C2B2 LL team and fill in the Logbook for this event.

Action 2.8

Hand out or send the evaluation form to the participants (e.g. via SurveyMonkey), ideally at the event or within 1-3 days after the workshop, then capture and analyse the results.

2.7 Documentation of LL workshop outputs

Developing a common vision will only be possible if adequate time is provided to discuss with all involved stakeholders: (1) the characteristics of the specific social-ecological marine system identified and analyzed and the main problems pre-scoped by the C2B2 LL team (*discuss Action 1.2 and 1.3 in the C2B2 launch workshop*); and the (2) the desired participatory ocean governance to be achieved and the transformative changes needed to achieve it in the specific area of intervention (*discuss Action 1.4 in the C2B2 workshop 2*).

The common vision consists of a list of:

- (1) the problems that are shared among all stakeholders and are recognized by everyone as worth to be address;
- (2) the desired shared outcomes to be achieved collectively.

Note: the required transformative changes and activities for addressing the agreed problems and achieving agreed outcomes will be co-created in the Explore stage (Stage 3).

Action 2.9

Based on the discussions in the LL workshops, formulate the LivingLabs's Common Vision in Annex 7, and then share it with the LL participants.

ANNEXES of Part 2

Annex 1 – Social-ecological system identification and context analysis

Case Site	C2B2 LL team responses
<p>You have ‘placed your site on a map’: How was the location for the case study chosen? For example, does it match a political or administrative entity? Or a geographical or natural area? Please specify and provide a brief description of the geographical location.</p>	
Resource System – draw on WP1	
<p>The case site you chose comprises a social-ecological marine system which is characterized by a specific resource system. The resource system refers to unmovable and undivided stock while resource units (see below) refer strictly to flow extracted from stock (Ostrom, 2015).</p> <p>A resource system is therefore characterized by ‘second-tier variables’ (McGinnins and Ostrom, 2014), including its <i>size</i> (e.g. geographic expanse, resource boundaries), the <i>types of resource sectors</i> (e.g. marine plant and fish species interacting with the system), and <i>human-constructed facilities</i> (e.g. off-shore platforms).</p> <p>Please briefly describe the resource system comprised by the specific social-ecological marine system under your consideration encompassing the aforementioned ‘second tier variables’ as much as you can.</p>	
Resource Units – draw on WP1	
<p>The social-ecological marine system under your consideration also comprises resource units. A resource unit refers to any type of good that is extracted or produced from the overall resource system under consideration (Ostrom, 2015).</p> <p>The resource units can be described through various ‘second-tier variables’ (McGinnis and Ostrom, 2014), including their <i>distinctive characteristics, spatial and temporal distribution, mobility, growth or replacement rate, interaction with other resource units, number of units</i> and their <i>economic value</i>.</p>	

<p>Please describe the resource units comprised by the specific social-ecological marine system under your consideration encompassing the aforementioned second-tier variables as much as you can.</p>	
<p>Governance Setting – draw on WP 3</p>	
<p>Governance Structures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does your site involve cross-jurisdictional institutions (e.g. basin organizations, nature re-serves)? • This C2B2 LivingLab will be affected by a range of laws and regulations. What are the levels of government in Sweden (e.g., local, district, provincial, national, EU)? • Which level(s) of government set or implement policies that regulate social-ecological interactions within the specific social-ecological marine system under consideration? • Are there non-governmental organizations for the offshore environment? • Are there existing network structures related to the offshore environment? 	
<p>Governance Strategies</p> <p>In the social-ecological marine system under consideration for this case study, there are specific institutional, financial, risk management, physical planning, and participation strategies that regulate social and ecological interactions. The following questions will help to disentangle the governance strategies regulating the specific social-ecological marine system under your consideration.</p> <p>Institutional strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What laws/norms/regulatory frameworks regulate social-ecological interactions and marine spatial planning in this case study? • Who ‘owns’ or coordinates the decision-making process in the offshore environment of this case study? - Who has the legal authority to decide? • What roles do the different governance structures (see above) have? How are 	

<p>these roles established? How is coordination among these different structures enabled?</p> <p>Financial strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What public funding is made available to incentivise human activities in this case study, and, if so, by which public entity/authority? • How this public funding is regulated and under which authority/(set of) norm(s)? • How are private investments regulated and under which authority/norm? <p>Risk management and physical planning strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation strategies (e.g. preparedness to climate change and wider system change) are in place? • Which public entity/authority regulates marine spatial planning in this case study, and under which norm(s)/regulatory framework(s)? • Do such norm(s)/regulatory framework(s) impose consideration of environmental and social risks and impacts associated with marine spatial planning and anthropogenic pressure from the existing (or new) blue economy sectors in your case study? If so, under which formal procedure? <p>Participation strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is public participation in marine spatial planning regulated? • Who has a formal right to participate - who is usually asked to advise? • Who controls what can be discussed in formal decision-making processes [related to the issues of your case study]? • Are there public channels to raise issues or comment, or is access to policy debates restricted? • Do you need to observe formal rules or understand technical or political language to contribute? 	
<p>Social Setting – draw on WP1 T1.3</p>	

<p>Beyond the resource system, resource units and the governance setting, the specific social-ecological marine system under your consideration is characterized also by multiple actors and their activities (e.g. off shore installations and actions and/or land-sea interactions).</p> <p>To help grasp this, please answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What relevant actors operate in the area and to which resource they depend? • What were the main past human activities implemented? • And the main current ones? • Are there major vulnerable groups, and/or ethnic or tribal groups, different languages, or religious, social or cultural sub-groups? 	
Economic Setting – draw on WP1 T1.3	
<p>The human activities considered above create specific economic value, relationships and power. Economic power strongly influences policies and coupled social-ecological interactions.</p> <p>To help you grasp this aspect, please answer the following questions and give a brief explanation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there major employers or concentrated industrial clusters, ports or special economic zones? • What blue economy sector can be considered as the most influential ones? • Which ones as the most vulnerable? 	

Annex 2 – Preliminary problem scoping

Preliminary scoping of the main problems		3. How does this problem affect the resilience (i.e. ability to cope with crises) of the social-ecological marine system? Illustrate the risks and impacts these problems create on the ecological and socio-economic resilience of the social-ecological marine system under consideration	
		Ecological resilience	Socio-economic resilience
1. In the ecological domain (i.e. resource system, resource units)	Problem 1...		
	Problem 2 ...		
	Problem 3 ...		
2. In the social domain (i.e. governance setting, social setting, economic setting)	Problem 1 ...		
	Problem 2 ...		
	Problem 3 ...		

Annex 3 – Planned timing of C2B2 LL set up and implementation

	Stage 1 Prepare		Stage 2 Form		Stage 3 Explore		Stage 4 Embed		Stage 5 Evaluate & Sustain	
	Start	End	Start	End	Start	End	Start	End	Start	End
Planned completion of activities										
Actual completion of activities										
Comments/ explanation										

Annex 5 – Generic session design for the C2B2 LL launch workshop

Agenda Item	Timing	Activities	Purpose and Desired Outcome	Who	Technical Implementation
Intro & agenda	10 min	Welcome of participants Present objectives & agenda Distribute GDPR consent forms	Clarity on objectives & structure of this workshop GDPR consent forms signed	Facilitator	slides
What's a LivingLab in C2B2?	15 min	Present LL definition (in C2B2 context), all 3 C2B2 LLs, and principles of LLs	Participants understand what a LivingLab is (in C2B2P context) and what activities it entails Principles of working in LL agreed	Facilitator	slides
Who's who in our LivingLab?	50 min	Activity: who's who (by quintuple helix sector) at [demo site]- participants use posts its to write down requested details, then state who they are & what is their relation with/interest in ocean governance at the site.	Participants get to know each other & their respective roles, esp. re. groundwater mgt		Post its Pens Flip chart
Break	20 min				
Real life context of our LivingLab in [location]	45 min	<precise activity to be decided>	Participants' perspectives & experiences related to the socio-ecological system in the site C2B2 team obtains sound(er) understanding of the real-life context of the participants	Facilitator C2B2 LL team	Post its Pens Flip chart for clusters of successes & challenges
Socio-ecological systems challenges at [location]	45 min	Laymen's introduction (and discussion) to the demo site's socio-ecological challenges and the main problems pre-scoped by the C2B2 team	Rationale for C2B2 approach to have LLs work through (some of) the challenges	WP1 expert	Slides
Break	20 min				
Scoping our LivingLab in [location]	30 min	Present the draft LL time line and the draft LL ambition, highlight extent to which LL can/not address all identified challenges Activity: scoping the [demo site] LL ambition – participants use post its	Participants understand what activities the LL can entail and available resources from C2B2 to support these Ambition of the LL agreed Commitment to forming the LL	Facilitator C2B2 LL team	slides

Agenda Item	Timing	Activities	Purpose and Desired Outcome	Who	Technical Implementation
		to write down their comments on the LL ambition, then share their comments, facilitator discusses, LL team combines/adjusts text ad hoc (on screen)			
Working together	15 min	Present estimated timing of activities (overall LL life time), ask for comments Guided discussion: identify preferences for working together	Practical aspects of working together agreed (timing; online/F2F meetings, email)	Facilitator	Slides
Wrap up & next steps	15 min	Summarise main progress of the meeting, give heads up for next LL meeting (online/F2F) Finish with group photo!	Clarity on next steps Commitment to participate in the LL in the long run.	Facilitator	Slides

Annex 6 – Reflection on LivingLab workshops

1. On this page, please complete the summary information in the table below for each LivingLab event to create a cumulative overview of all events held for the launch and further implementation of the LivingLab at your demo site.

Logbook entry #	Date	Title of event	Location
1			
2			
3			
...			

2. Please create a copy of the logbook (i.e. a new logbook for each LL event), then include it in this Annex (8) and complete it with the LL team during a joint debriefing session (ca. 45-60 min.) that immediately follows the implementation of LL events.

The logbooks help to capture important information about the LL context, effectiveness of the LL workshops and insights & lessons learned that will then feed into subsequent LL events. It also ensures that inputs for the continuous evaluation taking place in T6.1 are available.

LivingLab event logbook	
Event information	
Event entry # & title	e.g. #1 e.g. LivingLab Kick off workshop
Event dat	
Event location	
C2B2 team	(names, orgs, role in the event)
Stakeholders present	List of participants (name, org, role in groundwater management)
Objectives of the event	<p>1. <i>internal objective(s) for the event:</i> e.g. launching the LL, creating commitment to work with C2B2, identifying stakeholder challenges at the demo site</p> <p>2. <i>List objectives as presented to the workshop participants (on the slide deck)</i></p>
Evaluation by participants	

Participants feedback (e.g. comments received during event)	
Participants feedback (online/paper-based evaluation form)	<p><Overall scores/comments, to be entered once received></p> <p><link to completed evaluation form entries (excel)></p>
C2B2 LL team observations and assessment (joint reflections)	
Physical environment	<p><i>Notes regarding the suitability of the event space, ability to engage with stakeholders, etc.</i></p> <p><u>Elaborations:</u></p>
Composition of the participants (who attended)	<p><i>Comments re. e.g. overall composition of participants, level of representation (e.g. per types of stakeholders from the quadruple helix + nature). Age & gender mix.</i></p> <p><i>Did attendance meet our expectations? Did we have the right participants? Were they the right stakeholders to achieve the event's objectives (as outlined above)?</i></p> <p><u>Elaborations:</u></p>
Memorable quotes from the discussion	<p><i>Please list the quotes and add: made by whom (name, organisation [participants, C2B2 team members])? Why was each quote noteworthy?</i></p> <p><u>Elaborations:</u></p>
Interactions during the event	<p><i>Did the participants have an equal opportunity to share their views? Was this due to our session design or other reasons?</i></p> <p><u>Elaborations:</u></p>
Suitability of event design implementation to achieve objectives	& Were the objectives of the event achieved? (select one answer):

	<p>Fully achieved/partially achieved/not at all achieved</p> <p><i>What worked well/not well during the event? How useful/suitable was the event structure? Were the right questions asked/activities done? What other implementation aspects affected the success of the session?</i></p>
	<p><u>Pros:</u></p> <p><u>Cons:</u></p>
Lessons learned	
Notes for upcoming C2B2 activities & events	
Emerging <u>objectives</u> for the next meeting with this set and/or other LivingLab stakeholders	
Required actions	
Required support	
Event materials produced	
Materials	<please list them here>
Follow up	<p>Digital copies of all materials produced will be stored in this CitiObs shared folder: <add link></p> <p>Responsible for uploading produced materials & linking to the evaluation form: <please add CitiObs team member(s)></p> <p>Due date: <please indicate date></p>

Annex 7 – Evaluation form for participants

Event title: <LivingLab Launch workshop in>

Thank you for participating in the <event title>. Please let us have your views and feedback on the workshop, so that we may improve future C2B2 events. This will take less than 5 minutes of your time.

Please respond to the following questions by ticking one box only for each question. You can also add your comments and feedback in each section.

Section 1: Workshop content

1. Overall, my satisfaction with this C2B2 LivingLab workshop was

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

2. The relevance of the C2B2 LivingLab in <demo site name> for the work done by my organisation is

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

3. The benefits of being introduced to the C2B2 programme are

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

4. The benefit of meeting/getting to know other stakeholders as part of this LivingLab is

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

5. Please share further feedback on the content of the workshop, incl. which topics/aspects you feel should be covered in greater depth in future C2B2 LivingLab workshops: _____

Section 2: Materials and methods

6. The workshop provided an opportunity to share information about the current situation re. groundwater management in <demo site name>.

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

7. Overall, the quality of the discussions and dialogue of this workshop was

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

8. Please share further feedback on the structure of the workshop and how we can improve: _____

Section 3: Workshop organisation

9. Overall, my satisfaction with the organisation of the workshop was

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

10. The usefulness of information shared was

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

11. The quality and the suitability of the event space was

High -5	4	3	2	Low -1	N/A
---------	---	---	---	--------	-----

12. Please share any further feedback you have on the organisation of the workshop and how we can improve:

Thank you for completing this survey, we appreciate your response.

Annex 8 – The C2B2 LivingLab Common Vision

Common PROBLEMS to be addressed		Shared DESIRED OUTCOMES to be achieved	
In the ecological domain (i.e. resource system, resource units)			In the ecological domain (i.e. resource system, resource units)
In the social domain (i.e. governance setting, social setting, economic setting)			In the social domain (i.e. governance setting, social setting, economic setting)

Annex 9 – LivingLab team minutes

For each LL team teleconference, please copy the generic structure for team minutes below and complete.

Generic structure (do not edit)

Meeting date, time:

Attendance:

Agenda:

Action Points from last meeting:

Minutes:

Action Points for next meeting:

.....